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**An Autoethnographic Analysis of Social Enterprise's
Advocacy Communication**

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Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

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Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **ALESSA SHAINNE L. HOSTALERO** with the title: "**AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL ENTERPRISE'S ADVOCACY COMMUNICATION**" is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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Biographical Sketch

Alessa Shainne L. Hostalero, Shainne as she is often called, is a social entrepreneur, a marketing and communication professional, and an author/writer. She is an advocate who focuses on movements for sustainability, education, and Climate Action among others. She is running her passion project, a social enterprise, Happy Shift PH (HS Organic Products), offering sustainable, Philippine-made, and locally sourced items. She is also a Co-Partner of Upgrade (Design + Concept), a design and marketing firm based in Manila, Philippines.

Currently, she also serves as the Director for Business Development and Linkages for the National University Philippines enabling the development of the institution through forging partnerships with local and international companies and organizations for the whole institution including its campuses; and ensuring beneficial market studies and forecast for the University's expansion nationwide.

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Shainne holds a bachelor's degree in commerce with a major in Marketing Management from Far Eastern University – Manila (FEU), and a Master of Development Communication from the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU).

She earned various certification programs from prestigious institutions such as in Journalism (focusing on Social Change) from the University of California, Berkeley (UC Berkeley); Entrepreneurship (User Innovation) from Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT); Media Literacy from Arizona State University; and, Digital Branding and Engagement from Curtin University, Australia. In addition, she also finished her certificate in Sustainable Development under the SDG Academy and UN Sustainable Development Solutions Network (UNSDSN). She also holds a Six Sigma Yellow Belt Certification (CSSYB) and is a registered Author/Writer from the National Book Development Board (NBDB) Philippines.

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Shainne is a member of Greenpeace Southeast Asia-Philippines (GPSEA) and the Philippine Communications Society (PCS).

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Alessa Shainne L. Hostalero
Doctor of Communication, FICS
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Dedication

*This whole journey and dissertation
are dedicated to my grandfather who has given me life
and invested in my education as his means of treasure and love:*

Luis A. Lim (+)

June 22, 1943 – July 8, 2023

We have made it, Pa.

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ABSTRACT

This comprehensive study on Autoethnographic Analysis of Social Enterprise's Advocacy Communication explored my journey as a social entrepreneur and a communication scholar, showcasing the evolving motivations, transformative shifts in purpose, challenges, through my life's experiences and exposures. In this research, I utilized vignettes, immersion, and reflection guided by theories and principles of ontology, epistemology, teleology, and praxeological positions. These key findings and contributions created knowledge that challenges some traditional research standards unmuting my voice to integrate personal narratives and empower the study through personal experiences as primary values of autoethnography to contribute to the field of social entrepreneurship and its context of advocacy communication.

Valuable insights in the research denotes silent empowerment as a fundamental factor in advocacy communication, as it centers its role on credibility, lasting impact, and authenticity especially in the digital landscape. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in this said context uncovers positive workplace behavior as a crucial aspect in the success of an advocacy and of an any organization. Moreover, this study also concluded that digital platforms are fundamental for advocacy communication. It recognizes the paramount significance of technology in identifying markets, reaching broader audience, and effectively communicating an advocacy of a social enterprise. Storytelling and leadership are also remarkable results that this research was able to unveil. The importance of both signified a positive reception of advocacy from the audiences and considered key tools that affect insights, behavior, and culture of a market or an organization especially in the field of social entrepreneurship.

Through my social interactions and reflections in social entrepreneurship and past journeys leading to it—in this comprehensive delved of knowledge and experiences, I was able to gain insightful and remarkable definition of what social entrepreneurship specifically is: **Social entrepreneurship** refers to pursuing purposeful and socially driven business process with equal prioritization to its profitability. It surpasses traditional corporate social responsibility approaches, as it is not merely an auxiliary business afterthought but centers its conception and existence on its social causes.

This research concludes a reflection on personal growth and overcoming doubts and overall challenges in business, furthering the role of being an advocating and integrating it with entrepreneurship. Silent empowerment in this study affirmed as a powerful conduit that places value on actions and behavior as an essential consideration in advocacy communication in the field of social entrepreneurship.

This autoethnographic study enriches knowledge of the intricate relationship between social entrepreneurship and advocacy communication. This research did not only address research questions but also provided practical insights for those piloting the dynamic landscape of social impact through advocacy communication in a social enterprise.

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Research Title

An Autoethnographic Analysis of Social Enterprise's Advocacy Communication

Background of the Study

Social enterprise (SE), in its widest definition, is a *"business with a twist,"* (BC Centre for Social Enterprise, n.d.). It is a business model that focuses not only on doing business or acquiring revenue but in doing so, it centers on solving social problems. Social entrepreneurship has a distinguished difference from traditional entrepreneurship as it incorporates social causes and enables social efforts to the business model to improve quality of life, introduce innovation, and serve the community, to name some of its service goals.

In the Philippines, a variety of SEs – Non-Government Organizations (NGOs), cooperatives, social businesses, Micro and Small Enterprises (MSMEs), and other community-based organizations—concentrate on offering social and sustainable solutions. While there is a visible growth and demand for SEs in the country, there is a lean quantity of studies or research about them. Thus, such exploration, like this research, may expound more on what SEs are and how they accomplish their advocacy communication. Social Entrepreneurship is one of the most imperative ways to drive social change as it broadens business and social objectives about cultural,

social, and environmental goals that are more apparent and often seen in the voluntary sector (Pearce and Elkington, 2020).

This research discusses the advocacy communication of a social enterprise from an autoethnographic point of view to know how an SE accomplishes its advocacy communication from the view of an SE owner or the social entrepreneur. In a few lists of research about SE, specifically on the topic of advocacy communication, this study aims to provide a conclusion that discusses inclusive patterns, ways, culture, and phenomena that may also help social entrepreneurs in the country to know and explore the drivers of advocacy communication of SE and its impact on oneself and the advocacy. As a social entrepreneur, my experiences and exposure to SE will be comprehended in this study. Such activities and events from my SE's establishment will also concentrate on how my enterprise's advocacy is assembled, conveyed, and delivered.

There are many evocations of pleasant memories and challenges in this study as a social entrepreneur, and all I must say, are contributions to how my SE functions as a whole and how its activities are being accomplished to this date. As a scholar, I believe autoethnography would be the right method to ensure a rich delve into my experiences as a social entrepreneur. Such experiences, while presented to various institutions as an invited resource speaker, especially in the last two years, maybe deemed quite marginalized as only a few individuals are engaged in research about social entrepreneurship in the Philippines. There are only 164,473 MSMEs doing social entrepreneurship (Habaradas, 2022) out of 816,759 registered MSMEs in the country (ADB, 2022). While I am included in the mere 20.14% of SEs classified under MSMEs that have the power to provide and be provided interference in creating and

conveying advocacy and technical support to further scale up; not all I can say is engaged in identifying how advocacy communication is being accomplished; and with this gap, conduction of research related to the context of social entrepreneurship, its advocacy communication, are deemed significant to this field and to me as a social entrepreneur and a communication scholar.

Autoethnography

I take the most recent study by Cooper and Lilyea (2022) on using Autoethnography in this research—a qualitative research method that remains rather mysterious to many scholars. Autoethnography is a useful method to introduce a radically new source of information—own lived experiences (Livesey and Runes, 2018). I have seen that autoethnography has inherent flexibility and creativity in terms of demonstrating quality and meaningful results. Autoethnography places emphasis on *auto-*(self), *-ethno-* (the cultural link), and *-graphy* (the application of a research process).

This study concentrates on the narrative tradition emphasizing the story and pivotal experiences (p. 197), in this context, as a social entrepreneur practicing advocacy communication. According to the authors cited above, autoethnography shares:

A ‘storytelling feature’ and thus engages with other genres of self-narrative but therefore transcends mere narration of self to engage in cultural analysis and interpretation.”

This qualitative method fills a gap in most traditional research—where the researchers' own voice typically is not overtly included as part of the research (p.198). Thus, autoethnography concentrates on the base unit of “I,” as an author and the researcher—more so, reveal more of myself as the core of the study. This research shall craft creative narratives out of my personal experiences within advocacy communication in social entrepreneurship to ensure autoethnography's core of being an observational data-driver phenomenological method of narrative research, which aims to demonstrate and provide tales of human cultural and social life that are all striking, compelling, and evocative to best contribute to the body of knowledge from a researcher's or author's perspective—someone who practices in the field and has exposure and experience to the context being discussed (Poulus, 2021). This research shall articulate my personal knowledge of a cultural experience (Adams, Ellis, and Jones, 2017)—in this context, of social entrepreneurs in the practice of advocacy communication.

Research Problem and Questions

Social entrepreneurship is an emerging business model that has a huge potential and therefore has abundant opportunities to capitalize on in order to address social challenges, reach developmental goals, and achieve financial sustainability that intentionally constructs and provides positive social, economic, and/or environmental impact (Asian Development Bank, 2019). Given this palpable potential, there has not been much research examining the advocacy communication of SEs, especially in the context and view of social entrepreneurs. Therefore, this research aims to craft compelling and comprehensive accounts of how an SE, through the lens of the social entrepreneur, accomplishes advocacy communication.

As a guide and to give light on the research problem, the following research questions shall reflect the focus of the study:

1. As a social entrepreneur, how do I accomplish my advocacy?
2. Why is silent empowerment a key social and cultural factor in my advocacy and social entrepreneurial activities?
3. How can I contribute to the field of social entrepreneurship?

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this research is to provide a highly personalized narrative or account of an SE's advocacy and its communication from my view as a social entrepreneur. This is to present my experiences, practices, and beliefs that impact advocacy communication, and to analyze key social and cultural factors that impact my advocacy and the SE's other entrepreneurial activities. Such narratives aim to serve as a guide to aspiring social entrepreneurs and sustainable development practitioners, hence, this research aspires to be presented to a larger audience, especially to undergraduate students to inspire and encourage them to pursue the field of social entrepreneurship and embrace its meaning and potential that may be able to address and answer to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). My goal is to put a definition of what social enterprise is and how advocacy communication is commensurate to its overall pursuit.

Part of my objective in this study is to also analyze how I, as a social entrepreneur, since my mere days in 2016, have influenced its landscape and my understanding. Through this research, I am to showcase how SE and advocacy communication impact both the enterprise and the social entrepreneur, and how advocacy communication can be a relatable and encouraged concept of communication in this field.

Significance of the Study

Optimistically, this study can be a source of inspiration and a plausible source of data in terms of SE in the Philippines and advocacy communication as a substantive area in the view of the social entrepreneur. Most research in this field often dealt with the view of the market or the consumer in terms of how social entrepreneurship should be done and how they perceived the products, services, or offerings of an SE. Advocacy communication, per se, is a useful tool to translate advocacy goals into a project action that policymakers, national government, and local government units (LGU) can support to enable programs, vet policies, and establish financial backing for SEs in the country (ADB 2019, p.2; Haft, n.d.). This research will also enable fellow social entrepreneurs and colleagues to reflect on their own SE advocacy, its communication, and their career actions to reflect how they accomplish their own advocacy, the overall impact of their experiences towards social causes, and other cultural challenges that affect their own entrepreneurial responses and advocacy. As a social entrepreneur, of course, my goal is for the national government to further support and encourage assistance and establishment of social enterprise and ensure proper taxation and government resources are prioritized to further grow the field. Though all those goals might already be given and even lobbied by several advocates and organizations like the British Council Philippines, the Asian Development Bank, and the Philippine Social Enterprise Network, to name some, how advocacy is being accomplished is also pertinent to merit support. Knowing how advocacy is done can breadth further strategies, growth, and empowerment to both the market and the social entrepreneur.

Scope and Delimitations

This autoethnography analysis of SE's advocacy communication focuses on the researcher's personal experiences as a social entrepreneur within the social and cultural environment of SE. It explores the researcher's exposure, practices, and beliefs that impact the SE's advocacy in social, economic, and environmental pillars of sustainability. This entire research probes into the researcher's reflections, narratives, and analysis of advocacy communication and advocacy activities and experiences which aims to provide an in-depth understanding of scenarios, narratives, practices, and understanding in doing advocacy communication and its accomplishment from the perspective of a social entrepreneur.

Delimitations:

- Personal Perspective: This research is limited to the researcher's perspective and personal experiences as a social entrepreneur being this an autoethnography research. Thus, it does not aim to supply a comprehensive analysis of the entire SE as a business model and advocacy communication as a field but rather focuses on the researcher's unique and sole journey, exposure, reflections, and insights.
- Specific Advocacy Context: This research delimits its scope to a particular and limited social or cultural subset where the research has engaged her advocacy communication and advocacy efforts. This study may explore backgrounds in environmental sustainability, charity efforts, literacy,

education, social marketing, and communication as specific areas that provide a detailed examination of the researcher's experiences.

- Sample Size and Selection: Due to the personal nature of autoethnography as a research method, this research cores on the experiences and reflections of the researcher. The research does not seek generalizability but rather aims to provide rich and in-depth insights and narratives as a social entrepreneur.
- Subjectivity and Interpretation: This research acknowledges the subjectivity implicit in the autoethnography approach of this study and the inherent potential influences on the researcher's interpretations and biases. Thus, it highlights the reflexivity and transparency in the researcher's perceptions and discernments into the contexts involved, cited, and discussed. Some data, especially of those in childhood could have absence of photos and other diary inputs due to the length of time and lack of access to technology and devices in the 90s and early 2000s.

By recognizing the scope and delimitations, this autoethnographic research delivers a clear understanding of the researcher's experiences, social and cultural themes of exposure, and the limitations of the study. This allows the researcher to examine and present experiences in SE, advocacy, and advocacy communication in a transparent and meaningful approach as a contribution to the developing understanding of SE and advocacy communication recognizing and comprehending the unique perspectives offered by autoethnography.

Theoretical Framework

This research theorizes advocacy communication in reference to Cornejo and Kam's (2022) Advocacy Communication Theory (ACT) as a "*complex process consisting of advocacy strategies at the individual, interpersonal, community, organizational, and/or policy levels,*" that theorizes advocacy communication as *always communicative*—may it be conscious or unconscious, verbal and nonverbal, and explicit or implicit—thus, matter on how advocacy communication is being accomplished. In my social entrepreneurial experience, being an advocate first before establishing an enterprise helped and birthed me to be an entrepreneur with a social cause, and later found that social entrepreneurship does exist and that put a label on what I specifically do and what I should be specifically called or summarize how I shall describe myself when asked. In this theory, *silent empowerment* could be a new understanding probing Cornejo and Kam's ACT that advocacy communication is always communicative, thus, all, in consideration as to whether there is verbal or lack thereof and to the extremes of unconscious manner. In line with this, same as how Cornejo and Kam narrate on advocacy communication, advocacy communication strategies include daily communication—in this case, explaining to friends, classmates, colleagues, students, and audience on seminars I am invited to.

Conclusively, this research attempts to demonstrate that *silent empowerment* can be collective to both the individual (I, as a social entrepreneur) and interpersonal (people, stakeholders) which converges from advocacy communication and its communication and psychological factors combined.

Operational Definitions

Advocacy –public support of an idea, plan, or way of doing something (Cambridge Dictionary, n.d.)

Advocate – a person publicly supporting or recommending a particular cause or policy (Oxford Languages, n.d.).

Advocacy Communication – a strategic communication plan and action to deliver effective messaging about the advocacy of a social cause, a complex process of advocacy strategies.

Autoethnography – research method of the study that describes the personalized genre or field of the writing of the researcher or author which denotes his or her experience to present an understanding of a specific subculture.

Social Enterprise (SE) – a business model that can be either for-profit or non-profit. Adopts usual business practices but gives more importance to advocacy and social mission (Habaradas, 2022).

Social Entrepreneur – a person who practices, engages, and owns a social enterprise; a person who seeks business opportunities that have a positive impact on the community, society, and the world (Peek, 2020).

Social Entrepreneurship – the process of individuals and/or entrepreneurs providing business solutions that directly address social issues (Peek, 2020).

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This review of related literature aims to explore and examine the existing scholarly articles, journals, and related studies on SE's advocacy communication and gives insights into this specific entrepreneurship as a field and a business model albeit limited. Social enterprises bring a significant economic impact due to their processes that provide innovative solutions to address social issues and initiate transformations (EU, British Council Philippines, ESCAP, PhilSEN 2017; Habaradas, 2022). By analyzing and synthesizing relevant literature to this study, this review seeks to identify key themes, concepts, and gaps in the currently existing knowledge, supporting the understanding of advocacy communication within the realm of social entrepreneurship. Exploring related studies helps me as a researcher to underpin what is there to find out still and what research gaps still need to address; hence, creating a good foundation of how autoethnography supports the objectives of this study and answers its research questions.

Primarily, I analyze social entrepreneurship, its social and cultural impact, and the local Philippine setting of such for better resonance. Finally, I delve into advocacy and advocacy communication, its definition, settings, and how social entrepreneurship correlates with advocacy and its drivers. These three main areas of literature support the qualitative method of inquiry of this study as it is associated with autoethnography.

A comprehensive literature search was conducted utilizing various academic databases and official organizations' websites related to social entrepreneurship in the Philippines, social entrepreneurship as a field per se, advocacy, and advocacy communication: British Council Philippines, Asian Development Bank, International Journal of Business and Management Studies, and the United Nations Development Group (UNSDG) to name some. This literature supports the foundation of sources and alignment on the chosen topic. Thus, autoethnography, as a methodology, banks on related studies to engage notions correlated with the research focus and learn research gaps to validate and pursue the study.

Social Entrepreneurship in the Philippines

Representative Lorenzo "Erin" R. Tañada III (2012) described social enterprises (SEs) in his **House Bill No. 6085** or **An Act Ordaining the Promotion and Development of Social Enterprises in Order to Ensure Poverty Reduction, Providing the Mechanisms Therefor, And For Other Purposes** or the **Magna Carta for Social Enterprises**, as,

Organizations that are engaged in providing goods and services that are directly related to their mission of improving societal well-being. It generates profit or surplus with due regard to social and environmental costs and makes a proactive contribution to resolving social and environmental problems (p. 1).

For SE to fall under this definition, House Bill No. 6085 enumerated the definition and qualification befitting to be considered as an SE. Some of its conditions involve SEs to *"invest a substantive part of its surplus, profits or mobilize other resources to assist the poor, make a proactive contribution to resolving social and environmental*

problems and generate profit or surplus with due regard to social and environmental costs; employ any of the following development strategies in the pursuit of its social mission: 1) empowerment strategy; 2) social inclusion strategy; 3) intermediation strategy; and resource mobilization strategy; reinvest part of its surplus or profits back to the SE to sustain the fulfillment of its social mission; registered, shall be 100% owned and capitalized by Filipinos either in single proprietorship or partnership, and shall neither be a branch, subsidiary or division of a private enterprise” (p.8) to enumerate a few.

Social entrepreneurship in the Philippines may not be a new concept; thus, it combines the function of typical charities and typical businesses. They deliver social value to the beneficiaries of the social mission, practice funding, or grants to sustain themselves and scale up (Ebrahim, Batillana, and Mair, 2014). In developing countries like the Philippines, SEs often operate in far-flung poor areas, and cater to disadvantaged groups -- farmers, fishers, indigenous peoples, and the urban poor (Habaradas, 2022). SEs engage in different socially responsible programs or philanthropic activities with the main purpose of addressing societal issues. Poverty is one of the major problems in the country due to low to moderate economic growth; unemployment, job quality, failure in developing the agricultural sector, high inflation rates due to crises, increasing population, persistent and high levels of inequality based on assets and income, natural disasters, environmental poverty, and low economic expansion (Asian Development Bank, 2009). SE, an emergent business model, often addresses poverty alleviation. According to the collaborative report of the EU, British Council Philippines, ESCAP, and PhilSEN (2017), social entrepreneurship in the country has taken off and has even tripled in its population

compared to the last decade alone. Furthered by the study, the recent spike in the number of SEs was led by youth leadership as prevalent new entrants in the field, joining the 35 to 44-year-olds, the usual age of social entrepreneurs in the country. In addition, SEs are empowering women by creating platforms and employment for them; statistics show that 56 percent of those who are employed in SEs are women and 44 percent of SEs are led by women (p.12). Financial constraints are the primary concern of SEs, especially those start-ups, capital, cash flow, and funding are considered barriers to scaling; however, a significant percentage of at least 25 percent denotes that understanding and awareness of SEs and the causes they advocate are considered a quandary (p.13). While SEs in the country play a pivotal role in employment, poverty alleviation, and community empowerment, raising awareness of SEs' social causes, support encouragement, and increasing understanding of their overall role and function are still necessitated (p.15).

The Enormous Potential of SEs

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDGs) aim to transform the world through seventeen (17) interlinked objectives for people, the planet, prosperity, partnership, and peace. The UNSDGs were formed during the convention of the Head of State and Government and High Representative in the United Nations (UN) Headquarters in New York on 25-27 September 2015, during the organization's 17th anniversary. Formerly known as the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), UNSDGs or SDGs aim to address the unfinished business, hence, between 2015 and 2030, SDGs commit to alleviating social, economic, and environmental issues such as poverty, inequalities, discrimination, health, and energy crisis, deterioration of the planet and its natural resources, sustainability, and

economic downfall. These ambitious goals envisage freeing the world from such confrontations and commit to the development through an additional 169 associated targets that are indivisible and integrated (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, n.d.).

Figure 1. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the United Nations

The year 2023 is the midpoint of the implementation of the 2030 Agenda since its implementation in 2015. There has been reported progress in different areas of SDGs; however, some may still need to work on targets due to slow movement and regression (United Nations, 2023).

According to Chia and Lim (2016), “*Social entrepreneurship is a viable and significant way to nudge the world closer to the attainment of Sustainable Development Goals,*” such is a promising approach that facilitates and improves the economic, social, and environmental well-being, as well as the improvement of global health. In addition, social entrepreneurship showcased flexibility and

versatility due to the adoption of several principles—business management principles and the development of affordable, cost-effective, and efficient solutions to social issues and challenges. Social entrepreneurship, in all considerations, and comprehensive review of related studies, often only engaged in business and entrepreneurship fields, and limited studies showcased the relations of SEs' potential in sustainability areas aligned with SDGs. Nevertheless, if the SE itself tackles goals pertaining to and pertinent to SDGs, its global impact could also be substantial (Littlewood and Holt, 2018).

More and more businesses, even existing large corporations, consider inclusive growth through addressing citizenship and social impact—two of the roles of how an SE operates. They embrace the paradigm and character of SEs of going beyond revenue and profit and delving into understanding operations in a viable ecosystem and establishing relationships (Bersin, 2018). According to the Institute of Entrepreneurship Development (2020), SEs truly can be different from other or typical businesses as they can further create value through many different approaches such as:

- Use their profit to accomplish social and environmental good,
- Seek and craft emergent solutions and new ways of processes to address social problems,
- Focus on innovative use of business technologies and resources that can address social issues and challenges,
- Employ commercial business strategies to maximize improvements and transformation in human and environmental well-being,

- Work towards social, cultural, and/or environmental causes to ensure the creation of sustainable and efficient efforts for the people; and,
- Further community engagement, re-establish community-based economies, and re-invest locally to empower the local community and not to already wealthy stakeholders or businesses.

Indeed, SEs showcase a real massive potential in terms of business operations and influences of SDGs as they function significantly through unselfish causes that go past monetary benefits. With all these given social entrepreneurs or those who own and operate SEs may be then considered advocates—propagating, fighting, strategizing, implementing, and supporting causes related to sustainability pillars of social, economic, and environmental.

Advocates as Social Entrepreneurs

Social entrepreneurship has been defined over and over as a business model engaged in producing social goods and processes that go beyond profits and revenue. Actors of social entrepreneurship or social entrepreneurs share a common interest in alleviating social issues which they may not be able to accomplish if they are not advocates themselves. Social entrepreneurs or entrepreneurs doing business for social good have a positive influence on the development of SEs, their network, expertise, intersections, resources, and collaboration are essential factors that support the SE ecosystem (Lundberg and Nyström, 2018). Through social entrepreneurship, advocates can better support their advocacy toward a social cause as, often, they also aim to engage with media and media platforms to ensure

validation and relevance of the support they support. Media advocacy, it can be called, puts matters on the public agenda and encourages media (may it be mainstream and digital, as what everyone can utilize and witness today) to raise awareness about the cause, its possible solutions, and actual problems (World Health Organization, 2007).

Social and Cultural Challenges in Social Entrepreneurship

The world is still recovering from the COVID-19 health crisis and socio-demographic and lifestyle changes also affect entrepreneurs. Thus, the post-pandemic recovery still needs to be strategic and revitalizing for both the entrepreneur and the community or target market (Ratten, 2020). Baporikar (2017) explains that *“social and economic progress is inextricably intertwined,”* and social entrepreneurship addresses and occupies both. Yet, cultural challenges may also be complex for SEs. Baporikar’s question also bids on the division between a typical businessman or entrepreneur compared to a social entrepreneur. Citing it from the author, can it be that business entrepreneurs are to the economy and social entrepreneurs are to the society? (p.2). Both types of entrepreneurs are driven by pursuits to identify, have, and work for a vision, and gather a rewarding process towards an idea—regardless of whether they are working for profit. What distinguishes social entrepreneurship is its primacy towards a social benefit and its ‘mission-related impact,’ (p.5). Due to social and cultural challenges that, perhaps, SEs may be having difficulty fathoming and addressing, some boundaries must be considered—social service (up to what extent can an SE cover; community engagement (how many can resonate and the level of resonation), and market and purchase behavior (sales, revenues, and profits are essential to ensure SEs are

viable and sustainable in the long run). Seda and Ismail (2019) study the different challenges SEs face, though, set in Egypt, such may be universal as cited too in reports by ADB, the British Council, and PhilSEN. According to the said study, aside from institutional and operational challenges, SEs are also at the forefront of social, educational, and cultural awareness challenges—SEs are not widely recognized yet even though it is an emerging business model. Such emergent would also mean some nuisance due to the factors that it may not be widely marketed yet, zero to minimal public policies, and lack of government support in terms of taxation, encouragement, and knowledge-building towards the public. While social entrepreneurship is a promising hope for addressing socioeconomic challenges, culture building must also be considered and prioritized to ensure that the public or the right target market of an SE can better understand the enterprise's goals, purpose, and vision. Understanding such may equate to market support and eventually breathe more advocates.

With all these given, support for SEs and social entrepreneurship per se does not derive exclusively from the public. Characteristics of social entrepreneurs themselves are also critical in this emerging field; thus, it is evident that cultural context has an impact on entrepreneurship—and, cultural factors, for the record, can shape entrepreneurial activities, intentions, and attitudes, not only of the public but also other current and aspiring entrepreneurs or social entrepreneurs (Ariza-Montes, Morales-Fernandez, and Sianes, 2015). Social and cultural challenges and even economic difficulties in the context of social entrepreneurship in developing nations or third-world countries like the Philippines may also demonstrate that formal education (in a formal institution) and positive perception of character and/or

personal values could increase the probability of an individual to be a social entrepreneur (Hidalgo, 2020). In the Philippines where the education crisis exists, there may be fewer individuals who would not understand how SEs work, not about social entrepreneurs per se, but the reception of the public on how SEs convey their message, their advocacy and conduct business above all.

Advocacy Communication

Servaes and Malikhao (2012) share that "*advocacy communication is now a key action term in development discourse.*" While advocates are indeed issue and program-oriented, participatory advocacy is necessary.

"The ability to communicate is essential to the success of any undertaking and an important factor in the achievement of its objectives. We have entered an age of knowledge, and the key to accessing and harnessing that knowledge lies in the ability to communicate," (Research Matters).

Advocacy communication is defined mainly as influencing a specific market and utilizing a particular message to deliver changes in either policy or practice (Coulby, 2010). Furthermore, this type of communication requires clear objectives, knowledge of the intended audience, language appropriate for the said audience, and concise content. This could also be true for my social enterprise, Happy Shift PH, lobbying on a type of advocacy of formal presentation of research and recommendations to the public sphere and thus aim to influence other people or the target market to profess support to the advocacy being explained and educate them on the developments of such.

The utilization of external communication channels or vehicles is proven effective for advocacy communication. Some examples are usually Press and Print through newspapers, magazines, newsletters, posters, and advertisements; online--the most often used in this digital world through websites, blogs, email blasts, SMS/Tweets, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok; radio, and television; and direct speech--as practiced in my SE: presentations, seminars and workshops, conferences, and presentations.

Advocacy communication is not only for non-government organizations (NGOs) but also for SEs as the field and the business acumen practice legitimacy and credibility - two of the crucial components of not only effective advocacy but also an enterprise. This type of communication is a dynamic process, and such has no single formula for success but rather sharing a goal, gathering policy and political information, establishing credibility for advocates, and linking advocacy to business priorities (Health Action International, 2019) --this latter part is true and accurate for SEs.

Advocacy communication and its theory is an emerging field of study. Often, in Advocacy, Communication, and Social Mobilization, advocacy and communication are separate fields. Advocacy communication, per se, is a complex field in communication that goes beyond being an advocate and a communicator but rather combines both to create a more in-depth understanding, convey, and persuade people towards advocacy, sometimes regardless of social and cultural norms, and sometimes fitted to such norms to be duly entertained by the public. Thus, doing so, persevering through, and continuously accomplishing such could

mean a breakthrough and could give meaning to how advocacy communication is indeed about.

Information, rightful at that, can create a shift in the society or community being managed or influenced. Through communicating with a specific purpose and outcome in mind, advocacy communication takes place.

There are many ways in which advocacy can be communicated—and there are silent ways in which the empowerment of a cause can take place. Several communication techniques could also be remarkable for communication scholars and/or advocates who would want to engage in advocacy communication practices—and such are 1) listening more closely to understand; 2) using rich descriptions and analogies to improve audience empathy and understand any complicated information they may have; 4) modification of communication plan depending on the response of an audience; and 5) using verbal and non-verbal (voice and body language) to craft a sense of trust with the audience. (Hoffman-Longtin et al., 2018).

Advocacy Communication in a Social Enterprise

There has not been much discussion and studies about advocacy communication specific to social entrepreneurship. Rather and often, communication and social advocacy are topics that may be related to this field of learning this research is trying to discover and share. In fact, the most relevant to such is the study by Villar, Grande, Sandoval, Fadri-Francisco, Suva, Barroga-Jamias, Custodio, and Mercado (2011) about communication in selected social enterprises in the Philippines. Thus, the study notes that communication is one of the criteria that can be utilized to measure the social impact of social enterprises and

play a vital role in the success of these kinds of enterprises in the country. Case and cross studies research designs revealed and determined the view and/or concept of communication by social entrepreneurs. Communication, perceived in the said study and proven, has been a tool used by SEs in the country and is essential to the process of their operations, and any organizations, at that. Communication in SE is being utilized to maintain and strengthen relations with stakeholders and to promote the initiatives of the SE to the public—thus, it is still viewed as a process that has stages to accomplish to ensure the sustainability of the enterprise’s operations.

According to Naimi (2020) in an article, SEs are vocal about what they stand for; thus, they are able to publicize their work—in retrospect, social entrepreneurs are considered activists in their own right and way, working in an objective to pursue change required to create a more sustainable and just community or society. In plain sight, SEs are able to perform such acts of activism through their product or service offerings—such contributions are considered innovative and even provide an example to bigger for-profit companies and enterprises. Furthermore, it is believed that not only through products and services a social enterprise can create and establish impact but also through how communication is being done. Its communication practices are considered essential and may be able to influence change. More often than not, SEs are actively engaged in various conversations about topics they are passionate about and advocating for. They are aligned with pressing global issues and indeed vocal on what they think not only as an enterprise but also as an activist or an advocate pursuing the way to their desired social change. Social activists, in fact, have used advocacy as one of the drivers and/or their main strategies toward change. They create several narratives that are

informational, educational, and attention-seeking; thus, often, SEs proactively engage with the media to ensure the promotion of their desired solution to problems and challenges at hand. SEs combine the processes of typical business and social activism to mobilize stakeholders and audiences so that they may be able not only to offer their products and services but also to educate and bring in more people to support their advocacy.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

In my years as a communication scholar, narratives, stories, and reflections empowered me to pursue research, whether class-related or independent. In doing so, it gave me an edge as a social entrepreneur to further put into writing my experiences and insights for the benefit of my audience and posterity. I am exceptionally grateful that my doctorate welcomes more and more qualitative research as there are life and work exposures and experiences that are best shared when telling a story and giving light to rather formal terms in communication and research. When I was first starting in the doctorate program; in fact, when I first set foot in my graduation ceremony for my master's degree, I knew I would do this research, it has been rigorous years of polishing what could be the best story to tell as a social entrepreneur that shall inspire and influence fellow practitioners in the field to share and tell their experiences for the benefit of many. When I first encountered autoethnography during one of my classes in *Communication Research Methodologies*, I knew it had to be my method. It was two full semesters of reflection on how my dissertation shall be and the methodology or approach I should use to explicitly share my experiences that can contribute to the field of communication and social entrepreneurship. Most of my colleagues do think that I am extroverted given my exposure to marketing, communication, and customer service, but I am rather introverted hence it is a challenge and an advantage to be a social entrepreneur in this competitive field. However, after my years in development communication and in the doctorate program, I came to analyze and reflect, on

perhaps, that coming up to how I want to interpret such experiences in my advocacy and social entrepreneurship, I know I should be guided by acquired knowledge to help me elucidate such scenarios that could have a contribution to answering the research problem.

Guiding Theories and Assumptions to the Research Process

This qualitative research is guided by philosophical assumptions of *ontology* or ‘what we know’ and *epistemology* or ‘how we know it’. Such are results of beliefs and experiences developed and acquired through our lifelong involvements and learning—thus, privileged the perspective of “I” in this research. Through these assumptions, *teleologically*, the acquired in-depth understanding of personal narratives and the assumption of their reason and ends will navigate on the purpose they serve rather than the cause by which they rose; and that *praxeologically*, as a social entrepreneur, will create liberty to free once were muted perspectives in this field I have passionately worked on since 2016. Aside from knowing and assessing how I accomplish my advocacy from a social entrepreneurial perspective, it would be advantageous to know who I am in relation to this research, which, perhaps, fellow practitioners in the field of social entrepreneurship ask themselves, too.

These guiding theories and assumptions form the foundation of this autoethnography research; thus, enabling me, as a researcher to further explore and understand my personal experiences while contributing and delivering pronounced and broader knowledge to understanding social and cultural underpinnings of advocacy communication from a social entrepreneurial perspective.

Data Collection

This research constitutes data from my personal experiences as the source of information. Thus, it shall be collected through a combination of *external data* (e.g., *documents, presentations, speakership content, reports, etc.*), *self-reflective data* (*journaling reflections*), *self-observations*, and *jotted-down observations*. Such data to be included in this study is rightfully helpful and addresses factual, social, and emotional elements there may be (Cooper and Lilyea 2002, p. 199). To remain steadfast to a combination of descriptive-realistic and confessional-emotive style and context of the study, a chronological sequence of events in my social entrepreneurship knowledge and encounters to ensure how such events and/or activities contributed to the cultural self-discovery, to describe such conditions of these occurrences, and explicate the reasons why are significant in my life and career as a social entrepreneur doing advocacy communication (p. 200). Some non-linear order of events may be cited to give emphasis on the experiences and viewpoints. Artifacts of documents since the beginning of experiences towards the subject shall be presented and included for further analysis.

Reflexivity

Throughout the writing of this autoethnographic research, it is essential to recognize my position and its potential influence on the research process. As the primary researcher and author of this study, I present my personal experiences, insights, and biases assertively. I am a social entrepreneur, an advocate, a volunteer, and a marketing and communication scholar who has

personal and work experiences in the aspects of marketing, advertising, and participating in advocacy in and out of my SE.

These given aspects and views have shaped my perspective and understanding of the cultural and social elements under investigation in this study. I acknowledge that such interpretation of mine and analysis of the data presented in this research are influenced by my independent and subjective lens. Given such circumstances, as an autoethnographer, I am to embrace independence and subjectivity and engage in *critical self-reflection* to strengthen the validity, authenticity, richness, and depth of the findings.

By acknowledging my position and engaging in reflexive practices of transparency and open inclusion of my emotions, feelings, and sensations during the course of memory generation, I strive to enhance the credibility, clarity, and trustworthiness of this autoethnographic research. I invite all readers to critically engage with the findings, considering that such is the product of both my insights gained through personal exposure and experiences and the broader socio-cultural contexts that this study investigates.

Data Analysis

This storytelling through a narrative analysis to honor my own voice, focus on storytelling, and recognize that stories play a vital role in meaning-making and will be helpful for me to interpret my experiences (p. 202). Analysis of the data in this study is chronological and marks significant life events, learnings, and turning points. These experiences are continuing and thus, may not involve a clear resolution to a journey, yet, but thus, actively drive to *make sense*. This analysis involves examining structures, themes, and content within the narratives, activities, and anecdotes that transpired. The narrative analysis aims to reveal the underlying interpretations, meanings, and substances embedded in the narratives or the storytelling.

Given such, this autoethnography is evocative. Thus, aims to be meaningful and accessible for the readers. This study is both transgressive and critical as it is grounded in personal experience that stimulates the audience to the field/s in the subject and what it may and can represent that able to deepen one's acceptance, empathy, and understanding of larger or wider societal constructs (Bochner and Ellis, 2016).

Data Set and Research Undertaking

This study includes pieces of memory, recollections, and anecdotes, presented as vignettes, from social entrepreneurship and advocacy experiences. These vignettes are supported by outside data (certificates, Facebook posts, blogs, notes, emails, DCOMM outputs, etc.). These transcriptions are presented in chronological sequence beginning with my experiences as an advocate, my

development work, my exposures, straight to being a start-up enterprise, advocacy communication activities, and transformation to being a social enterprise and a social entrepreneur. Thematizing and sense-making transpired during the writing of vignettes and reflections are presented. Such narratives and analyses aim to probe *silent empowerment*, the breadth definition of a social enterprise, advocacy communication is an essential element to the pursuit of social entrepreneurship, and how these factors can contribute to the field.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents the results and discussion of my autoethnographic study about the analysis of my SE's advocacy communication. This research aimed to provide a highly personalized account of an SE's advocacy and its communication activities and to put a definition to what is social entrepreneurship, especially in the Philippine context, vignettes are presented in this section. As I progress in the study viewing advocacy communication and SE, there are three themes relating to the research questions: *advocacy communication*, *silent empowerment*, and *social entrepreneurship*.

As previously stated, I started as an advocate focusing on development work to become an entrepreneur and eventually transformed into a social entrepreneur. My professional experiences are aligned with marketing, entrepreneurship, and communication through degrees I have earned and my corporate, and academic experiences.

Through vignettes, this chapter presents the reflexivity points that influence my SE's advocacy communication highlighting the following results:

The use of digital platforms and some behavioral instances of introvertedness in entrepreneurship.

- Technology plays a vital role in empowering both the growth of the business and its advocacy communication,

- Digital mediums and outlets like social media and e-commerce websites advance the reach of the SE to its audiences; and,
- Technology helps and supports anyone—whether introvert or extrovert—to connect to various individuals and markets regardless of their background and exposures; hence, creates a new discovery of audience and situating the right target market through advocacy communication strategies executed.

Social Entrepreneurship as a journey.

- Childhood experiences, upbringing, and college exposures shaped my experiences in pursuing advocacy and business interests.
- The enterprise cores its existence on a strong foundation of social mission and responsibility that later on involved and realized social entrepreneurship—an emerging field of business that integrates entrepreneurship and social causes' solutions.

The Influence of Silent Empowerment in Advocacy Communication

- Silent empowerment has a crucial role in advocacy communication as it discreetly empowers the audience which eventually leads to long-term advantages of fostering cultural and societal changes.
- Through silent empowerment in advocacy communication, the advocacy is communicated through inspiring, influencing, and leading by example may it not be explicit in verbal communication, but highlights the non-verbal communication strategies.

Contributions and Meaning of Social Entrepreneurship

- Silent empowerment in advocacy communication in an SE creates and builds credibility, empathy, and authenticity toward the goal of social change.
- Leading by example cultivates a culture of purpose, resilience, flexibility, and adaptability, and creates opportunities for involvement, which all constitute success.
- The power of storytelling through actions.
- Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) ensures its significance in advocacy communication of an SE in promoting positive and impactful social change through behavioral changes and alteration.
- Social entrepreneurship, through anecdotes of experiences and learnings, means focusing on socially driven business practices that equally prioritize profit to ensure stability and sustainability of the SE for the benefit of the social cause and its primary stakeholders; and,
- SEs' existential foundations cored on social causes that sought sustainable and innovative solutions in resolving social causes and introducing solutions that also ensure financial viability to sustain and further social impact.

This chapter presents the pertinent literature and discussions of an SE's advocacy communication—silent empowerment as a strategy and results in one, the transformative power of storytelling through actions, and the significance and impact of social entrepreneurship in driving social change.

I. Advocacy Communication

Vignette One

“The #NoToStraw Experience”

#NoToStraw campaign initially started when I was still in college taking up my Green Marketing course. The said course opened my eyes and my being to be an environmentally responsible marketer which also constituted our group then, [to do] research [about] using plastic utensils in University Belt, its effects, and its alternatives.

Truth be told, I also happened to have lost [track] [of] what should have done in the first place. It is very recently that all these woke me up again and finally initiated a campaign for the greater good. When I started supporting campaigns for the ocean, it triggered me to be more responsible and hands-on [with] what should be done for the environment and its entities. Besides, we are the beneficiaries of our own efforts and sacrifices.

*My #NoToStraw experience seems to bring weirdness for some. As an example, the baristas who serve me coffee or Frappuccino—to be more specific—used to find it really different that I go for a **no cover, no straw, and no tissue** Frappuccino. They tend to ask me why, and I, on the other hand, enthusiastically [explain] to them what it is for and what benefits we could all get by limiting our plastic usage. Others were convinced, the rest just found it funny. From my end, at least, my trash, whenever I order coffee, is just the plastic or paper cup—just one from the usual many things that were being thrown away whenever I dine in or have it to-go.*

True enough that is hard to totally eliminate our plastic usage, but we can start by limiting the consumption of it. Just like for straws—we can still drink our beverages without [them]. I know that it provides convenience especially if it is a cold drink as the ice is going straight to our lips, but limiting its habitude can provide a greater convenience not just for us but for the environment as a whole.

Immersion to Vignette One

My first memory of going into business started when I was in fifth grade owning a makeshift grocery store or a *sari-sari store* with a toy pushcart sponsored by my grandmother. My clientele only involved cousins from the compound where I reside. I grew up separately from my immediate family, my mom raised my brother in a separate home in Caloocan, I was in Valenzuela with my maternal grandparents, and my dad was and still is an Overseas Filipino Worker (OFW). No one in my family is an entrepreneur—all, I know, are OFWs and corporate employees. At 10-11 years old, I enjoyed selling albeit introverted and a shy kid. Such interest in entrepreneurship led me to take a ¹bachelor's degree in commerce and I majored in Marketing Management beginning in the year 2008. In 2009, as a second year in college, I was introduced to Marketing Research as one of the major courses in my program, and this subject was an inaugurating period towards development work or being an advocate. As part of the course's requirements, students in the class need to be grouped and form their research that must be proposed and defended. We were a group of ten students, and I was the leader. The study was entitled ²*"A Study on Effects of Consuming Plastic and Styrofoam Materials Used in Selected Fast-Food Chains in the University Belt,"* a quantitative research study that aimed to know the ³effects on the environment of the usage of Styrofoam materials and plastic as eating utensils. During the course of the research, I grew a huge interest in reusable materials as they trump more benefits to the environment, especially in the University Belt (U-Belt) area in Manila, where trash, garbage, dirt, and the drainage system are the main concerns specifically in the early 2000s and early 2010s.

In 2010, Typhoon Ondoy hit the Philippines, I was part of those students who got stranded at U-Belt for 24 to 48 hours. I have witnessed immense flooding and

poor drainage systems that also stemmed from the amount of garbage in the area that clogged sewerage in the City of Manila. That incident intensified my aspirations towards advocacy to benefit the environment.

In the academic year ⁴2011 to 2012, as a fourth-year college student in the Green Marketing course. My then sprint of advocacy aspirations has been fueled as the subject opened me to be an environmentally responsible marketer. I graduated in 2012 and took many forms of career explorations—firstly, in advertising, retail, and training. In 2014, I was invited to join the academe, thus, the schedule in the academic institutions permitted me to go back to causes I am passionate about and volunteer in organizations that match my interest as an aspiring advocate.

In early 2015, I joined as a ⁵volunteer and a member of an NGO with the goal of ensuring the ability of the earth to nurture life in all its diversity. During my free time or day off, I participated in various campaigns for the oceans, climate action, zero-waste, and sustainable living. In December of that same year, I started my graduate studies focused on Development Communication. All those drives to pursue more development work and study more about it stemmed from the programs I participated in, conferences and roundtable discussions about the environment that I attended, my reflections as a college student studying in U-Belt, and experiences in natural disasters like typhoon ⁶*Ondoy*.

With these exposures and participations, I always reflect on things that I can do and how I can contribute to the environment and local community per se, given that we are beneficiaries of our efforts and even our sacrifices, my interest in entrepreneurship and my professional experience in marketing and communication was fueled more through these reflections. In 2015, I envisioned starting an enterprise with a mere Php5,000 in the bank and in an 18-square-meter apartment.

In January 2016, my enterprise debuted selling mainly alternatives to plastic and single-use items—reusable stainless straw sets, reusable cotton rounds as make-up removers and for skin care use, and all-natural cosmetics and soaps sourced locally from community retailers and small businesses.

Reflection on Vignette One

Experiences are the Roots of Advocacy

Early exposure to entrepreneurship, environmental case studies and related literature, and experiences in natural disasters like typhoon *Ondoy*, ignited my interest and curiosity to further these factors and integrate them into how I live my life and pursue experiences related to it on both personal and professional levels. Indeed, these influences inspired me to engage in activities and eventually advocate for causes that had an affinity with me through integrating them into how I follow through with my life and even circumvent my path towards it eventually led to me opening an enterprise that communicates and advocates for such integrations—introducing alternatives to plastic and single-use materials that can ease our way to minimize garbage that goes to landfills and clogged sewage systems.

Immersion and exposing myself to topics and events on these aspired advocacies created a whole different persona in me and gave meaning to my character as a person and as a professional. Hence, choices of paths like pursuing graduate studies to further my knowledge in development communication and practice my professional interest in entrepreneurship and marketing became the forces that breadth opportunities for me to explore.

Sensemaking: Dependence on experiences and environmental factors conceives advocacy.

Integration to Life

With such integration of aspirations and doings into my life, it has become an integrated advocacy and a sort of path I came to be immersed with and eventually, live. Integrated advocacy is a term used in civil society to describe an approach or strategies to powering social change that integrates and/or considers all change schemes, and leverages them sequentially, concurrently, and in combination to boost efficiency, overall impact, and mutual benefit (Bernholz, Ozer, Wainscott, and Elhai, 2020).

Since my advocacy has been largely dependent on the experiences and learnings I was exposed to, I also thought that if I had been shown other factors or exposed to a different scenario, I would probably have been interested in entirely different propositions. As a child, I realized that the environment and support you have growing up are a cogent determinant of what you will be when you grow up albeit also maturing and making choices of your own. My passion stemmed from the commencement of critical views based on my life's conditions and observations that badge my comfort and build worries. The impulse to do something is omnipresent and pressing as it provides satisfaction and fulfillment when done something to provide a resolve no matter how "low-key" or discreet. Passions of and for advocacy on the environment or other related subjects and development actions, alter my character and even created it in order to prompt actions benefitting others. Privileges determined and experienced when I was a child empowered me to share and integrate efforts into my life-long personal and professional path to, as "cheesy" as

it may sound for some, make a difference in the manner I know how and am capable of.

“I alone can’t change the world, but I can cast a stone across the waters to create many ripples.”

- Mother Teresa

Sensemaking: Making a difference as part of life’s purpose and advocacy integration.

Meaning Gained from Vig. 1: childhood, school learnings, and remarkable events are significant experiences that influenced my outlook and advocacy, and a start of silent empowerment within myself.

Vignette Two

“Appreciation”

Since I started our Happy Shift two years ago – put [it] on hold, then restarted again [in] April of this year, it was and still is a struggle. You need to research, develop, promote, do customer service, and always uplift the brand. Being a business major myself, many of my friends think it will be easier since I have a background. Perhaps, at some point, but never entirely.

I always believe that [hard work] will pay off and working smart is indeed the key. Also, I firmly believe that I couldn’t do it [without] the people around me who give their support even in simply [liking] my brand’s page, Facebook posts, or Instagram uploads. I also like to believe that there’s always good in everybody and that people are also willing to help you and not ask for anything in return, except for you to appreciate them.

I'm not close to success but I'm glad how things have started and gone its course. I couldn't say that I haven't experienced any tremors yet, but I'm proud to say I was able to jump on the hurdles because of the people around me.

I have big dreams [for] the brand. I want to convey its message to everyone and how it can uplift everyone's day while helping the advocacy toward [environmental] safety. Though there is still a lot to learn and discover I'd like to thank the people who made starting a little easier for me:

Crissy – for buying and trying almost everything without explanation from me about the product or where and how I did it. She's always excited to try the items even if it means she wouldn't get it for free. I want to thank her for taking her time in the day to tell her other mommy friends [about] the product and the brand that eventually led to more sales as per [usual].

Jocel and iTAG Manila – for suggesting what courier to use and trying out [products] as well. This group is also my inspiration [for] why I think I can come up with business ideas. It was their brave strategy, passion, and friendship that started everything about iTAG Manila.

Ross – for being about everything the product and the service [have] to go through. From doing all the package designs to even doing the dishes because there could be times when I'd be too busy sorting some of the products and checking how it was packed and all [sorts]. Thank you for lending a hand [in] everything [that] I need.

Genna – my makeup artist friend who isn't afraid to try local products like mine compared with those she uses for her professional gigs. Thank you for holding your workshop and promoting Happy Shift there. It means a lot to me.

To my friends and family—thanks, you guys! For [supporting] SMEs and going beyond [your] budget to purchase and try out the products. Thank you for sharing it through the power of word of mouth. It means a lot to me to know that I have your support.

Especially, to my clients! Thank you for not getting mad even when there's a problem with the shipping. Thank you for being the beacon or the glue that puts the brand together giving a chance to the product and crafting good reviews about it. I don't know how I can thank you enough for purchasing. I know that life today is hard because of the prices in the market, but setting aside a little money to try out Happy Shift means a lot to me.

I don't know how to thank everyone for being so supportive and advising me on what to do and how I can make work a lot faster and easier. Thank you so much, [everyone], for giving me the confidence, courage, and [strength] to go on. THANK YOU and I SO APPRECIATE all of you.

Immersion to Vignette Two

Starting an enterprise is never without a challenge. As a business start-up, ⁷*Happy Shift (HS Organic Products)*, with the advocacy of offering products that answer to the shift to usually consumed items, sourcing, logistics, and inventory is always a feat. When I started gaining clients, mostly mothers at first, it was easy to get the message across because whatever a mother does can have an impact on her child—hence, advocacy towards environmental conservation, utilization of reusable items over single-use ones, and locally-made products were simpler to market to fellow moms, as a mom myself. *Happy Shift* started as an electronic commerce or e-commerce brand based in Manila, Philippines, due to the lesser cost and growing online market. Marketing and branding of the brand were exclusively done online through digital platforms like social media, brand websites, and e-mail blasts. In 2018, I joined the ⁸Lazada Seller community, an e-commerce platform where brands and entrepreneurs sell their products with hooked logistics to support them. Aside from *Happy Shift's* website, Lazada Seller Center has been a key e-commerce tool that introduced my brand and my products to a wider set of audience nationwide. In early 2019, I joined ⁹Shopee Seller Center, another new entrant e-commerce platform, which is in competition with Lazada to boost sales and reach another set of markets in the Philippines. With the birth of e-commerce platforms like Lazada and Shopee—and the response of prospects and clients to my ¹⁰website at

www.happy-shift.com, sales have been fulfilling. These electronic stores or e-stores have been received well by my intended market and more importantly, funnel through the message of the brand regarding its advocacy that grew from being just *eco-friendly* and *all-natural solutions* to usually consumed products to *locally-made*, *locally-sourced* promise that also ensures support to organizations that aligned with the brand's premise and advocacy to support – environment and local community suppliers (e.g., saving Sierra Madre, Climate Action, Love Local, Support Local, etc.). To further understand the environment, its sustainability, climate, and other related fields that can help out a brand enforce advocacy communication, in 2019, I graduated ¹¹Master of Development Communication (MDC), and my very thesis about millennials' reception of climate change in the country helped me understand that current state on how they perceive the topic and its details. It helped me to craft more products and justified sourcing locally to ensure contribution to growth within the local economy and help local suppliers and communities to introduce and help their products flourish in the local market scene.

After my graduation my MDC graduation in 2019, I also immersed myself in ¹²social entrepreneurship through the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) Social Entrepreneurship Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs). The short course was also my first introduction to social businesses and somehow made me realize that what I currently do in *Happy Shift* falls on social entrepreneurship as also described in the program. Such exposure and learning helped me to further foster and shape my interest in understanding social causes and how I would be able to advocate for it more and incorporate its objective into my enterprise. In the same year until 2020, I also took certification in ¹³Sustainable Development under the United Nations Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN) and SDG

Academy and concentrated more on digital platforms to ensure that my products and advocacy can reach an audience albeit challenging because of the competition. When faced with difficulties and dilemmas due to market factors and being an introvert, I always believe and get inspired that communication, effective communication, will always be possible and of the essence when I utilize digital media to maximize the technological advancement we are served today. As an enterprise that is duly dependent on online platforms and the rise of far-reaching and serving logistics, they fulfilled that e-commerce could reach a wider clientele without the steep cost especially in my enterprise as an MSME. Facebook and Instagram have been useful in terms of reaching people and conveying messages as all markets can be tapped through the said social media platforms. More and more people—students, specifically, are reaching out to me via social media for sponsorships, resource speakership invitations, and purchase of products. All of this fuel the advocacy of the enterprise and am able to disclose what I do in *Happy Shift* what the enterprise is all about and why it is here. The enterprise is for profit but seeks local communities to ensure that all products being sold are locally made and locally sourced. More and more, as the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) also promotes local products, *Happy Shift* is in support of this, too, but I ensure that all products are sourced from marginalized communities in the country, especially in the middle of the COVID-19 pandemic. Since I started the e-commerce business, the year 2020 has nailed the path for me. Since 2016, *Happy Shift* is only fully operational online and 2020 was supposedly the time that I am going to expand to have physical stores in Manila and Quezon City where most of my market are. The onset of the pandemic has changed the goal and the direction of my enterprise—a lot of businesses whether tiny or huge have migrated to having duly online

operations and hybrid work setups. Even I, as a full-time employee in the academe, saw this shift to the 'new normal,' and that made me realize that digital is the way to go. Prior to the first year of the pandemic, I thought that the reason I was not scaling up was due to the fact that I am only visible online, while I gain traction easily nationwide and even globally, I looked forward to having physical stores to ensure that my advocacy can tap wider set of audiences. The year 2020 paved the way for embracing e-commerce and reaching more markets all over the Philippines. As an advocate, I also live my life focused on the advocacy I support as I did in years before even the conception of *Happy Shift*, I try to lead by example with the people I work with or lead to on the academe, introducing to the helpful benefits of support local, mitigating climate change, advocating for the use of reusables, and supporting environmental efforts by NGOs and other organization. While it is difficult, more and more I get to meet like-minded individuals who carry the same advocacy even though they are far more introverted than I am, and this fact and experiences made me wonder and apprehend that perhaps, there is hope for ensuring reception and support for both the advocacy and its communication even without the built and innate noise as I was often exposed to in the field of business and marketing. In today's world, all people, regardless of their backgrounds and demographics, are considered digital creators, having been able to influence other people, no matter how modest in size. As an enterprise owner, I see the huge difference between advocacy communication and marketing among my clientele. Clients today, especially my millennial and mother market, are more vigilant and do comprehend the product and the brand's promise. They are more aware of the 'just marketing' type of promotion compared to the brand's advocacy. They wanted the business to be as transparent as possible even with its challenges and current undertaking. As

a marketing major and a professional, I see that they know if it is just marketing to promote a brand rather than advocacy to fuel the social cause and its stakeholders. I engaged with them on this due to the hefty feedback they provide on my enterprise's social media platforms and e-commerce stores. They are generous in giving their thoughts about the products purchased and my brand's advocacy that they also support. In fact, about seventy percent (70%) or seven out of ten of my clients try out and order products from me due to its social cause and advocacy rather than just merely trying the products themselves.

Reflection on Vignette Two

Electronic and Digital Platforms Enable the Business and its Advocacy

Happy Shift's advocacy communication of supporting local products and efforts for the environment are being communicated through digital platforms such as e-commerce or e-stores, social media, and e-mail blasts. In my experiences since the conception of my enterprise, digital outlets have been the primary if not the sole platforms of conducting business and delivering the brand's message. The advocacy of the enterprise is communicated by encouraging the market and educating them to embrace reusable and locally made items that provide 'shift' or better alternatives to usually consumed products or tools. It works that all resources whether news or blog posts about *Happy Shift* are based on scientific and actual data and research that are crafted in a more understandable manner so the audience can fully grasp the message and its meaning. In addition, posting creative posts or publication materials or pub mats is helpful in shaping the market to understand the brand's promise and what and who will benefit if they purchase or support the products of my enterprise.

The use of technology has been advantageous because not only does it cut costs, but it also reaches a wider set of markets nationwide—one thing that I realize that a physical store could not. The onset and the experiences in the pandemic have validated all these efforts when all businesses whatever industry they might have shifted online and embraced fully work-from-home (WFH) and hybrid work arrangements. The digital platforms that I have utilized prior to the health crisis have also been utilized by businesses in various industries and even the national government. Collection of taxes, registration of businesses, and prioritizing MSMEs have become more prominent in these challenging times to ensure that the local economy survives despite the trials faced during this unprecedented time.

Sensemaking: Technology and digital platforms enable both the business and its advocacy.

Influence and Leading by Example

In 2020, I already know that what I am doing and advocating for and about *Happy Shift* is more than a Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). While I am for-profit, the core of the business is to advocate and support local communities and the environment where it centers its primary operation and the specific reason why it is conceptualized and conceived. As an advocate, in combination with what I have majored in college, these influences have inspired me to further my studies to learn more and be legitimate enough to also influence and lead by example. Whatever I have experienced, and I have learned, I get by through daily living by sharing them and learning more from like-minded individuals and even those who have opposite beliefs. While I may be introverted, digital platforms also helped me to gain feedback

about what I am doing right in my enterprise, and I was able to measure who gains knowledge and meaning from what I share in *Happy Shift* and how far it reaches. In organizations I am affiliated with especially those in the academe, I was able to practice advocacy communication by leading through example, by '*practicing what I preach,*' by bringing social causes I support, and communicating advocacy through incorporating it with the stories I share horizontally in the organization. My enterprise's social advocacy is communicated through influence. In this regard, advocacy communication is different from simply promoting or a mere promotion of a product or an entire business, but advocacy communication is also done through *leading by example* and communicating with people regardless of their ties and exposure to the social cause. I notice that the advocacy and the support that goes into the business are stronger when being communicated with fellow advocates or people who understand, are passionate, embody, and aim to create social change too—like-minded individuals, are what I call them.

Through digital advocacy communication, buyers, customers, and the market are all creators; therefore, they have a voice. More than making business or gaining profit, I do realize and comprehend while trying the enterprise flourish primarily aims to alter the way of life. Thus, it will be done through embodying experiences and sharing my personal beliefs and knowledge gains in every product being sold, in every advocacy communication to be done, and in every content I post.

Sensemaking: Advocacy communication through embodying
advocacy makes the business framework.

Meaning Gained from Vig. 2: Advocacy communicated through digital platforms has paved the way for how the business was enabled and how the enterprise became a social cause itself.

The Accomplishment of Advocacy Communication and the Idea of Being a Social Entrepreneur

My being an introvert with a business major has demanded new measures that can both practice my interest in having an enterprise without being duly face-to-face with people, in order for me to reach my dreams and professional goals. These two characteristics do not coincide especially if selling or networking is needed as it requires communicating with various individuals. However, digital platforms have empowered me to do both. The use of technology has been a key tool towards the propagation of my advocacy, enablement of finishing graduate degrees and certifications that could help me and more importantly, in the inception and development of my enterprise. Digital platforms like social media and e-commerce websites have created a place for my business to flourish and for my advocacy to be communicated not only to my target market (millennials and mothers) but also to other audiences (Gen Z, Boomers, etc.) and organizations, as well as local communities that I have employed and gotten affiliation with to ensure the business promise.

In the preliminary stages, as an advocate with business interests, I center my enterprise on what my experiences taught me and other learnings especially when I was in college. My college studies have been an awakening for someone like me

who grew up in the comforts of home in somewhat suburb then, in Valenzuela City, a province of Bulacan way back when, where everything was sheltered and often traditional as I was also residing with my maternal grandparents in a farm lot closer to nature than other suburban areas. With my exposures and upbringing that gave birth to my advocacy and being an advocate, my enterprise focused not only on being responsible but also on being equipped with the very core of addressing a social problem and advocating for a social cause. With this factor, it dawned on me that perhaps what I was doing was social entrepreneurship, given that I also had some theoretical background and exposure to what was supposed to be its meaning from certification courses and online programs. Martin and Osberg (2007) shared that the term *social entrepreneurship* starts with the word *entrepreneurship*, and the word “*social*” modifies entrepreneurship per se and its meaning. Everything in a business and even social enterprises at that, begins with an entrepreneurial concept. In addition to this, entrepreneurship is a direct action and a grasping of an opportunity with the possession of a creative solution. While social entrepreneurship can also be for profit, rather than money, it is spurred and driven more by altruism—the opportunity to identify, pursue a vision, derive a psychic reward, and the value proposition or the transformational and social benefit of the business.

At this point of my realization, I was starting to think that perhaps what I do is not just entrepreneurship but social entrepreneurship, but not fully yet as I would not want to self-proclaim a feat of what I do as an entrepreneur, and at that moment, what I only knew and focused on was the will for me to continue because my business is already gaining traction and have tapped and partnered with different local communities in Laguna, Mindoro, displaced mothers who know how to sew in Quezon City, and other small communities and entities in Cavite and Rizal. I also

started to work with different outsourced workers, who prefer to work freelance and not be bounded by time with a 9-to-5 work setup and would be willing to take in various clients. I was familiar with this setup because I, too, have worked freelance since 2010 when I was still in college and had to make ends meet to ensure I had an allowance on hand that I could use for some other needs I had for school projects and other school requirements. This was also the time that I knew that my entrepreneurial venture could do more as it not only offers local products, educates, and advocates for people about the current status and need of our environment and education, but also provides employment and a training ground for people who wanted to try work-from-home and hybrid setup—the setting I am full familiar with being able to study through distance learning since 2015 when I have taken up several certifications through educational institutions abroad and I started and graduated from an Open University.

Realizations and experiences from Vignettes 1 and 2 also point to advocacy communication through *leading by example* as it is also different from simply promoting products and advocacy through digital platforms like social media. It was how I adopted the advocacy that made more difference as advocacy is communicated through influence, therefore being practiced to further introduce solutions to social challenges that I was and still am determined to address. *Leading by example* also leans, attracts, and resonates with fellow advocates or people who are interested in the same cause, like minds as they are often referred to in conversations—as they understand, are also passionate, embody, and aim to create or contribute to the advocacy to create social change eventually. Through digital advocacy communication, advocates like me had a voice. More than making business, my primary aim has been to influence and even alter that way of life in the

market by embodying my experiences and sharing pieces of my beliefs in every product being sold.

In Fig. 1, my childhood, overall upbringing, and school experiences welcomed my innate passion and compassion to be an advocate. These exposures helped me realize where the roots of my beliefs and advocacy drives are. All factors and events led me to be an advocate and are elements that have urged me to accomplish something and communicate. According to sociologists, “childhood is socially constructed,” meaning that our childhood is influenced and crafted by society or the environment we are in, rather than being determined by biology (Thompson, 2023). Interests in business when I was a child and my experiences in school during my college years crafted an infusion that equates to establishing an entrepreneurial venture with a cause to fulfill. The environment or the society I was exposed to are determinants of what sparked and fueled my interest in entrepreneurship and advocacy. Challenging turning points and core experiences in my daily life have driven me to communicate such interests.

Vignette 2, on the other hand, showcased my realization that indeed duly online operations have helped an introverted person like me to voice out my advocacy and demonstrate my passion albeit silently and subtly. As an observation and input to these experiences, I on *Happy Shift* crafted a new form of advocating by focusing on action and focusing on actual work rather than concentrating on marketing alone. Thus, targeting fellow advocates and those who are interested in knowing more about my brand and what the enterprise is here creates new a new market behavior—that ultimately, unlike other brands I am competition with, *Happy Shift* is silent, it plans to stay the same, but all the more driven to communicate and advocate for its advocacy about the environment.

II. Silent Empowerment and Becoming a Social Entrepreneur

Vignette Three

“Is the Future Really Sustainable?”

Issues in the environment are not all new. In fact, such problems surfaced since the 19th century – the aftermath of the Industrial Revolution.

Technology and nature, on some levels, do not coincide. Coals have been utilized to support power supply that also supports types of machinery.

At some point (at least not so much in the current aspect), innovation or development equates to pollution.

As early as the 1950s, there were already attempts to raise awareness and spread information about the adverse impact of technological innovation on the environment.

The price people have to pay for the advancement of technology is increasing. Not that innovation cannot do humanity any good; however, development should not be at the expense of the existing natural resources and the entire community that relies on them.

Changes are evident in the seasons. Natural disasters, while inevitable, are extremely destructive and even getting far worse – putting many lives and resources at stake. The nation cannot seem to handle such extremity anymore. Hence, the attempt will advance the various disaster and risk reduction programs.

The national initiative of the government is vital to encourage people to engage and be informed of what they can do to abate the effects of climate change. While these initiatives are deemed essential, [the] promotion of sustainability and environmental protection shall be participated by local businesses and big corporations.

Tapping businesses to participate is necessary because they are the ones who produce massive supplies and [are in control] of heavy production for public or market consumption. In simple terms, they have the power to influence people. Thus, getting them to be more aware of the implications and existing atrocities of generating materials that can batter the environment is not only [essential] but should also be mandatory.

In return, businesses can also gain adherence from the market in promoting and achieving sustainability. Hence, it can empower their venture in the long run while influencing more and more people to participate. Many startups today leverage by promoting and encouraging the market to shift to using sustainable products on its excellent cause.

One hindrance [is] why businesses cannot or would not power through sustainability and eco-friendly initiatives because it could mean more expense from their end. What these companies do not see yet is the 'good cause' that makes them more preferable by the market while in a bequeath to support sustainability.

More often than not, businesses have more competence and power to influence people even more than how the government has done. Thus, sustainability and the potential to help the environment combat its issues could rely on enterprises (primarily, but not solely).

The future is indeed sustainable. It is not (at least not yet) a hopeless case. The government, [businesses] (whether big or small), together with the community should work hand-in-hand towards the goal of a sustainable future.

Technology-centered or driven companies could make use of the opportunities to lead business sustainability by making wise choices on how they consume energy and where they generate it.

Retailers and Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) companies can support this effort by averting the use of single-use plastics in their packaging.

Culling better alternatives to what was usually the best resort due [to its] economic advantages could be overwhelming at some point. The community should also [realize] that what is economical sometimes does not duly equate to being environmental and sustainable. Therefore, it can result in drawbacks and other complications—whether in health, finances, [ecology], etc.

Immersion to Vignette Three

As I traverse the entrepreneurial world and practice advocacy communication, focusing on educating and influencing those whom I can tap, fellow advocates, and educating students and other entrepreneurs who would want to adopt the same practice, I have witnessed and learned that businesses have the power to influence people and the industry. Sustainable practices can create a ripple effect that can modify a cultural norm and social construct when done broadly with consistency. In my experience, the most challenging matter I faced was the one thing I should be good at Marketing (advertising included). As a marketing major, there are many advantages to having been able to put up an enterprise, a socially responsible, at the same time; as advocacy communication plays a great role—more than having advocacy and social responsibility, but communicating it breaths inspiration and motivation that enables changing of the traditional narrative and having the opportunity to introduce and be accustomed to a new one, as also part of its goal. These struggles have been more evident to me due to the rise of more competitors that have been financial allocations or budgets. The *trend*, they gain *clout* better, and they gain more *followers* that convert into clientele. All these competitors of mine gain more traction on digital platforms on social media, educating the public can enable and promote more social and cultural change than

merely marketing and/or promoting a product. As a consumer myself, I am a witness to what some enterprises with the same scale as mine fail to realize or accomplish—such shortcomings also inspire me to be more socially responsible.

With such *clout* and audience, it was palpable to me that digital marketing using digital platforms like social media and other online outlets has a better impact than it was initially expected to be. All those who have social media accounts whether they are considered “*influencers*” or not are content creators and can enable and empower other people better no matter how lean or limited their “*following*” is. My experiences and exposure to different platforms, research, and organizations, especially NGOs, have kept me aligned with what we currently face, not only in the retail industry but also in national (and even international) social problems that gave birth to *Happy Shift’s* advocacy in the first place.

My advocacy has kept me guided. By looking at ways to bridge the gap of usually consumed items, and offer alternatives, to donate a portion of *Happy Shift* sales to causes or initiatives that share its belief and its passion, it delivered the will to empower. As an enterprise, I, personally, do not only support communities that manufacture products, but I also support my fellow small businesses in terms of purchasing and sourcing from them sustainably—whether it be through a form of local packaging or stickers. While this kind of for one is silent on social media and does not have to be content for everyone to know, this practice is constantly done and is sustainably well despite the convenience, affordability, and accessibility of other suppliers abroad like China and Vietnam. “Philippine-made” and “Philippine-sourced” are essential parts of my business mission and vision, and the enterprise’s promise. *Happy Shift* not only offers and sells sustainable and locally sourced

products of such with such promise but also adopted a whole different business promise that qualifies it to be a social enterprise rather than only practicing Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Using sustainable and locally sourced packaging is one of its triggers, alongside the whole mission and vision of the enterprise, its brand culture, and its brand pedagogy. My talks and/or resource speakerships, as well as my research and studies about retail and the natural environment and its problems, have helped me determine differences. At this point, it came to the picture that what I *might* be doing is social entrepreneurship.

Technology has a huge impact on my business process. Technology in communication has kept my enterprise alive—and such livable exposures breadth following, through the use of technology, too. I am surprised that many communities even in far-flung places (that eventually become my product suppliers) have also access to social media and other digital platforms albeit inexperienced. This fact has driven me to create more content that is universal to my target audience and to educate people about the advocacy and why I support certain social causes through *Happy Shift*. Despite the reticent style of marketing, I have gained followers and it worked to my advantage as the people who started following *Happy Shift* have already an inclination to communicate and support the advocacy despite the discrete method of marketing and promoting it. One client from Baguio City shared that *Happy Shift's* online presence has made up for its physical absence. She reviews the products I sell and she has become a repeat and loyal customer as she finds the products very effective for her and she is determined to keep ordering because she supports what the *Happy Shift* believes in and advocates for—and in this way, even if she is not personally putting up her own campaign and even her own social enterprise to make a wave of effort, supporting *Happy Shift* is making

her advocate, too, as she feels empowered and helpful whenever buying from my enterprise.

¹⁴Customers do highlight the packaging of my products as I use only kraft paper, jute strings, and other kraft and paper products. There is a future in sustainable packaging though a bit challenging as some items might need to have plastic bubble wraps for protection and plastic tapes for sealing; however, my consultation with couriers on such standard packaging styles for delivery has been answered, too, as they also allowed paper and boxes packaging for parcel deliveries but ensure that they are well sealed and tight for protection. Thus, packaging for businesses has been adjusted, and more and more fellow entrepreneurs have utilized sustainable solutions to wrap items. Businesses have the power to influence people as they are part of the basic unit of the economy. Hence, more responsible business techniques and processes must be adopted. This reality has been evident to me as an enterprise shifting to being a social enterprise and wanting to influence not only my fellow entrepreneurs but also the national agencies to craft support for these efforts.

Vignette Four

“Engagements”

*I'm getting anxious about a speaking engagement. Someone from La Salle called me asking if they could invite me for a speaking engagement because they are inclined to invite **social entrepreneurs** to be a judge for a HULT PRIZE competition. While I always believed that what I do is social entrepreneurship, that call somehow gave me validation that it is indeed social entrepreneurship that I'm currently doing.*

She said that I'm recognized and qualified to judge the competition for my efforts on sustainability, supporting local, and promoting Philippine-made products. With this, I was told

that I would be a good addition to the roster of judges who can inspire and assess the business proposals of aspiring young social entrepreneurs like [me]f. I feel honored, overwhelmed, and anxious all at the same time. In my years in the doctorate program, I feel it is illegitimate to call myself a social entrepreneur, so somehow, I also resort to introducing myself as an academic being employed full-time in an educational institution. But this call from La Salle somehow managed to legitimize what I had been doing for nearly a decade now, and I felt validated, certified, and justified that yes, these entrepreneurial efforts are social, too. And this is a good platform to know more about other efforts, sustainable at the same time, from people younger than me—students, who perhaps share the same vision as I am.

This is quite different from my previous talk with the same institution; however, this has triggered the recognition that these youngsters have bestowed, and I probably judge alongside real social entrepreneurs—people who admire and inspire me to be in the field of social entrepreneurship. Albeit silence they can empower and it made me realize that you don't have to be loud to empower and be recognized, you just have to consistently do what you think you do best and inspire change in anyone, and all these tractions and reach, I'm thankful that I have an active social media presence because I finally able to reach out people whom I know for sure I will be shy to approach in public. This is really one for the books and while I'm nervous, I'm excited to be part of this, too.

Finally, an addition to the many milestones of sharing what I do in Happy Shift. I can't wait.

Immersion to Vignette Four

There has been a lot of uncertainty, especially in the midst of the pandemic. Businesses like mine have been challenged to produce and sell products even with the rise of online selling and online shopping as more and more people have

tightened their budgets and spending due to unemployment and its possibility, illnesses, and even death. To cope with these challenges, I have opened myself more to opportunities, not only for my academic work but also for marketing *Happy Shift*. I did not have a full fund allocation for online advertising as I concentrated mainly on creating organic posts to cut costs and to ensure that I could still purchase from the communities I tapped and in connection with to also secure their income. While this was a long and hard feat, I have taken chances on bringing out myself more to be walking (though virtual) advertisement and to tap the audience, that for me has a lot bigger potential to be educated and be passionate about my advocacy (and this was how I communicated it moving forward),--the students, in Junior High School, Senior High School, and in college. I spoke publicly before, of course, call of duty in both work and in graduate school; though I'm used to presenting and speaking in front of a large group, I felt different talking about my advocacy and my enterprise. At some point, I felt more nervous, and I tend to be more perfectionist--probably due to the fact that I, and in this enterprise, are one and it felt like opening a whole can version of myself to people and aspiring to gain more advocates to share the vision and mission with me. My first-ever speaking engagement about *Happy Shift* and as an entrepreneur was with Senior High School students in Quezon City, Philippines in a homeschool arrangement. It was a career orientation highlighting my entrepreneurial experiences and how I was able to incorporate my advocacy into a full career. It was a delightful experience for me, and it sparked many engagements after. After a few months, I was invited to my first-ever international resource speaking engagement in ¹⁵Jakarta, Indonesia, to talk to Junior and Senior High Schools in an international school taking Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand about doing sustainable business and

being a socially responsible entrepreneur in an entrepreneurship seminar. Communicating my advocacy has been digital and virtual because of the pandemic, but indeed, there can be a wider set of audience when doing it online or hybrid because it does not put too much limit on how many people you can present to. I have gotten feedback from the organizers that students have spurred an interest in doing sustainable business and adopting socially responsible business practices, supporting causes that share their own aspirations and issues close to their hearts. It was not necessarily doing the same as what *Happy Shift* does, but it was sparking engagement for them to do something they feel strongly and passionately about, just like what I experienced when I was a child and when I was once a student like them. Repetitively, I have spoken about my advocacy, vision, mission, and entrepreneurial experiences in these avenues, and I saw that more and more students are sending me messages—that they have been moved by the topic and were inspired by the possibility of earning and doing something responsibly for the environment, the society, and for the community.

Speaking with High School students has opened more doors for me to elevate my platform. One College in ¹⁶Caloocan also tapped me for a speaking engagement regarding sustainable business, often referred to me as a ¹⁷*social entrepreneur* due to the business processes I adapt and the products I offer. While this was not entirely different from my previous speaking engagements, the audience was more enthusiastic to know about *Happy Shift* because it has opened other opportunities for them to explore that while my enterprise is for profit, it is also for a social cause, and that two factors still coincide with one another in order to deliver the promise of the brand.

Not long ago after my first speaking engagement with college students, I was invited to a bigger university, one of the top universities in the Philippines, to talk about *Happy Shift* as a social business to an entrepreneurship organization in the said school. I was delighted to be part of the program as I have realized that many educational institutions and student organizations have been interested in knowing more about sustainable business practices, social entrepreneurship, and how to incorporate CSR in every decision they make, especially professionally and categorically, in business. As usual, I was delighted as more students engaged with me in the forum asking questions specifically on operating with sustainable business acumen and how I would advise them if they were inclined to adopt such. Another eye-opener is that what I would do is for-profit but operational not only to do good but to be a concept of change in the retail industry and society. For me, that was one of the validations. After a few months, I received another invitation from the same university, this time, from a professional international organization that aims to convene students in various countries and compete worldwide. The organizer called me and inquired that they needed a *social entrepreneur* to be one of the ¹⁹judges of the business plan competition and that I was qualified to be part of the event as a social entrepreneur myself. I haven't been putting labels on how I manage and operate my enterprise, but indeed, being labeled by another entity seemed surreal to me. I was greatly honored to be awarded and recognized for my efforts as a ²⁰*social entrepreneur* and an *expert* when the program concluded. It was not the first time that I have been labeled as a social entrepreneur, but it was the first legitimate moment that sealed the deal for me. From there on, I did not feel like an impostor any longer as I have embraced being a social entrepreneur giving meaning to the term and concluding that *social entrepreneurship is also for-profit*

and it is not just about adopting sustainable business practices or going forth with social responsibility efforts but rather was made, established, and operational through and/or for responsible entrepreneurship, advocating, and communicating for social causes.

Reflections on Vignettes Three and Four

Validating Empowerment Through Behavioral Shift and Feedback

Verbal reviews and written evaluations or sent messages to *Happy Shift* validate the enterprise's effort and growth of its advocacy as evidenced by its following and increasing reach albeit more discreet and restrained compared to other brands or other enterprises in the same field or category. Through feedback, my efforts regarding my advocacy and its communication are being validated with the use of digital or online platforms. Such feedback merits to the business brought development plans and product innovation, and collectively allowed clients and intended audiences to have an outlet or an avenue of opportunity to communicate may they be anywhere in the Philippines and even around the globe. Access to the internet and social media have crafted a new way of birthing ease of communication whether positively or negatively it may be.

In Fig. 3, digital platforms play a huge role in getting feedback from my clientele and also seeing how they behaviorally shift even if they do not directly tag *Happy Shift*, but when they are chartered in using the hashtags and reposting my content on social media, this could be considered feedback, engagement, and reach for my enterprise and of course, my advocacy. Online platforms are also an avenue or tool for research as any element gained from clientele and interactions

with them can be considered a form of investigation and analysis to know more about the market behavior, market segmentation, and product development inputs through written and openly contributed recommendations from people.

While all information is available on digital platforms, the absence of online paid advertising, although has its own known disadvantages, has a positive effect on the enterprise, too. In *Happy Shift*, whatever clients I may have been already advocates for the environment or education someone who believes the good cause of advocating for these two facets, or budding advocates who seek information and have a deepening interest in social causes just like mine. My enterprise sells not only locally produced and sourced, supports causes, and functions entirely for advocacy and communicates it, but also the *belief* that inspires and inspires to create social change and behavioral shift to further the advocacy itself. While I may not be as aggressive as my counterparts or compared to various competitor brands in the same category, my lack of aggressiveness may not constitute a lack of assertiveness and boldness toward advocacy communication of what my enterprise tries and works hard to convey. I remain committed and communicative verbal or non-verbal through my actions and embodiment of what *Happy Shift* advocates to either explicitly or implicitly remark change and pursue the brand's social cause. Social media content is one of the primary ways of communicating advocacy and even gaining feedback from clients. Thus, the path towards such personification of the belief aims and performs empowerment to also empower the market regardless of the meant target audience and although not as loud as it was presumed and expected, but all the more carry on the efforts through discreetly targeting who these silent markets are. *Silent empowerment* has worked wonders in making my enterprise's efforts and advocacy communication neat, cost-effective, and

impactful; hence, the reason why through these years and even with the emergence of additional competitors in the market, *Happy Shift* is still progressing and gaining traction from various sets of still growing audience.

Empowering people even in a silent way does not mean incoherent, but rather aligned on the brand and the enterprise's promise, character, and entire delivery to existence. Such *silent empowerment* is aligned with the **Advocacy Communication Theory (ACT)** – referring to advocacy communication as *always* communicative – may it be verbal or non-verbal, explicit or implicit, conscious or unconscious, it has the power to empower people or audiences (Cornejo and Kam, 2022). According to and as expanded by the authors, *advocacy communication* is a “*multilevel process consisting of a different form of communication strategies/tactics across various channels,*” these channels can be interpersonal, mediated, or through any other forms that have the purpose of creating positive change on behalf of one's group, organization, or individual that is informed by one's past lived experience. With this, advocacy communication has varying degrees of costs, risks, benefits, reach, visibility, and efforts, because of a wider inclusion of modes of how advocacy can be communicated such as and not limited to social media posts, interpersonal advocacy, political advocacy, protests and marches, and even academic advocacy strategies that may formally or informally be organized and executed (p. 4). Fig. 3 highlights such empowerment through behavioral shift even in the absence or lack of marketing strategies pointing out that advocacy communication is greater than the perceived marketing tactic, and also proving that my enterprise, *Happy Shift*, is not merely doing it for marketing purposes, to sell, and gain revenue, but to also communicate an advocacy that may change perspective of people and aspire the said behavioral shift through also

supporting my product offerings and other social efforts for the benefit of the primary advocacy of the enterprise.

I am grateful for the feedback *Happy Shift* received whether it is a product review, an inquiry, or a mere suggestion of how we can improve more as an enterprise through private messages (PMs) and direct messages (DMs) sent to social media platforms, mobile numbers, and email addresses. Feedback, no matter its form, impacts my enterprise in more ways than—whether it is a subtle commentary of verbal feedback, demeanors showcased to us by our clients (e.g., repeat orders, bulk orders the next time they transact with *Happy Shift*, etc.), or non-clients support to our advocacy in the form of donations, sharing our content, or inviting me in various speaking engagements, have provided me a perspective and data that I can utilize to improve and/or innovate how I do business and what I offer to the market. Through advocacy communication, *Happy Shift* was perceived to have more depth and not only perceived as CSR but rather its existence as an enterprise is solely based and solidly formed through the advocacy. It is advocacy first, business second for *Happy Shift*. Feedback is one way of providing me, as an entrepreneur, an explanation of what I do right in a business without having control over the narrative. Feedback, whether verbal or written or non-verbal, assertive, or subtle even, is research data I use to see how I can traverse my entrepreneurial efforts to their betterment to ensure the life of the advocacy and gain more support from the growing audience and compete in the development landscape. The behavioral shift and the feedback I was exposed to because of my exposure and being duly involved in the enterprise give me a sense of validation that the flow of advocacy communication, the efforts, and the platforms are deemed effective rather than it is challenging. The benefits outweigh any inconveniences or risks on the part

of content-creating or crafting materials to educate, inform, and convey a message to the audience. Such validation gives a signal to continue empowerment though in a discreet manner because of its far worthy rewards of behavioral shift and ideal feedback from clients and budding advocates—it was noteworthy that whoever is interested in purchasing and supporting *Happy Shift* is well researched and has a heightening interest in its advocacy and are becoming agents of social change.

Sensemaking: Silence and unboldness also have the potential to empower people.

Meaning Gained from Vig. 3: Silent empowerment is aligned with ACT as advocacy communication is always communicative – whether it is verbal or non-verbal, explicit or implicit, conscious or unconscious – it has the ability to empower or enable people or audiences.

Enterprises have the power to change the game

Reflecting on my Vig. 4, I know that businesses and entrepreneurs have the power to change the landscape of our social standing in the country. The government recognizes top companies because their taxes are huge contributors to the country's fund that enables growth and progress in all aspects. These are all evident given how much they can strengthen and support the country's economy and other social needs. Hence, why there are so many expectations from businesses to perform their civic duties and support other government efforts because they have the power not only in terms of financial value but also to influence and inspire people due to their reach and higher following. As a business

graduate and an entrepreneur, I know and understand such dynamics. When I started *Happy Shift* with its advocacy in mind, social entrepreneurship did not exist to me yet, but as I go on in the field of entrepreneurship answering and existing to a social cause, I have started to accept that perhaps what I am doing is social entrepreneurship, until I have managed to open myself to various speaking engagements and opportunities that enable me to share what my enterprise and advocacy are all about and the exact entrepreneurial processes I adopt that also meant to inspire aspiring entrepreneurs of the new generation. While I know that I am not close to what tycoons have achieved with their businesses, I have come to accept that what I do, though not unique for many, has a heart to continue and help communities, educate, and ensure support to the advocacy that wishes to advance social change and behavioral shift to its users and intended audience.

It was heartwarming and validating to be referred to as a social entrepreneur by students who aspire to be one and pursue the field by choosing a degree program that answers to its call and understanding both technical and theoretical aspects of such. While self-proclamation may be easy and convenient, being bestowed with the term is more legitimate and confirming. The recognition is not only for labeling myself as a social entrepreneur, or the convenience of being able to introduce myself in a more convincing and accurate manner, but it also serves as an acknowledgment of my enterprise's efforts in this emergent and developing field. My recollection in Fig. 3 empower me to further believe that I am making a dent in this field, though quite unknown for many, but beseech to me as a pursuit. In the many ways I have been silent or discreet in my entrepreneurial endeavor and my advocacy communication style, the right people do recognize their own and as

much as I enable them towards the social cause, they enable me to further that social cause that develops the advocacy even more.

In this regard, businesses, whether huge or tiny, start-ups or established enterprises, have the power to change the landscape of entrepreneurship and local society, at that. While financial capabilities and resources could be an advantage for many entrepreneurs, lack thereof is not a hindrance to empowering and being successful in the field of social entrepreneurship, as its main focus is to empower individuals to convert them to advocates and support the cause, but also to the enterprise to offer products and services that equate to the efforts of the audience and the advocate convert. Businesses' and entrepreneurs' attitudes and personalities have been proven to spark change and create curves of innovation and improvement toward more sustainable and responsible business processes that can also ignite the same in society.

Sensemaking: Enterprises and entrepreneurs can manifest change whether positive or negative.

Meaning Gained from Fig. 4: Entrepreneurs have the ability to change the economic landscape whether for the better or for the worse. Hence, it is essential for the current and new generation of entrepreneurs, social entrepreneurs at that, to maximize the opportunities and the chance to influence and inspire the market towards an advocacy or social pursuit.

Silent Empowerment as a Key Social and Cultural Factor in Advocacy Communication of a Social Entrepreneur

Silent empowerment in terms of advocacy communication constitutes empowering people or the target audience even without noise and too much clout, but rather is focused on the real meaning and value of the advocacy through platforms that are most effective given the niche. As a result, silent empowerment captures the audience or convert-advocates who have an initial understanding of a social cause or advocacy. Through this, silence is honored and through efforts managed discreetly, empowering people silently ensures a deeper and lasting impact of the advocacy; thus, it can be a determinant or an essential factor in culture and society that harnesses and promotes participation towards a certain social cause.

“When a society (or a company) is healthy and growing sustainably, members of society (or employees) are more engaged and less prone to radical ideas or disengagement,”

This quote according to an article by Pastor (2019), referring to leadership and careers specifically of women, also denotes parity to how silent empowerment is an imminent element towards achieving a social goal, especially through social entrepreneurship. All entrepreneurs are leaders, but not all leaders can be entrepreneurs, social entrepreneurs, at that. As a social entrepreneur, who made peace on the label of being one, I also made accord on my own advocacy and activism—thus, allowing my profit ventures to create a positive change in society through advocacy communication and other communication practices (Naimi, 2020). Silent empowerment can be achieved through building a brand’s reputation and sticking to it. Both are hard processes to ace and get to and through, however,

there are many noteworthy rewards that it suffices—prospects to clients, clients to repeat and loyal customers, and loyal customers to full-pledged advocates. In my experience as a social entrepreneur, I saw these remarkable shifts and have served *Happy Shift* that quiet can also mean loud and silence can also be empowering even without too much marketing. Silent empowerment is organic and deep, it is reciprocal and mutually exclusive at times, albeit discreet. In fact, the silence deepens the understanding of one's advocacy and the receipt of the market towards operationalizing empowerment and the embodiment of the advocacy. Thus, as observed and experienced, despite the absence of clout and extreme advertising, silent empowerment is ever more rewarding because it is experiential, educational, and modest, therefore better and more sustainable in the long run.

As a social entrepreneur, or an entrepreneur, at that, reach and engagement, even *clout*, are factors for success. There is an impression that the more you are visible (as a brand or an enterprise), the more that you are capable. In my early years as an entrepreneur and a business and communication major, I know this one for sure—marketing and publicity make a business and serve as factors for business success; however, as trends change and generations take over, more and more millennials and Generation Z (or GenZ), are ambiently aware of their needs and more open about their preferences—whether brands or businesses like *Happy Shift* take it as positive, negative, or constructive. The latter is often considered because feedback and voice are being valued especially in advocacy communication—it is a two-way street, that advocates for and advocates from. Thus, all-encompassing, consider each feedback as a valuable asset to ensure, that despite the prudent and temperate style of communication, responses especially criticism are given attention to. Social and cultural elements such as silent

empowerment play a significant role in the outcome and elective effects on the audience's environment. Sociocultural factors play a crucial role in any individual's functioning and development, which also help divert their personal wiring to another behavioral shift (Melchert, 2020). In this sense, silent empowerment creates a new social and cultural construction that impacts the market consciousness as they have become more focused on their own voice, echoing their preference, and personally seeking enterprises and/or brands that resonate with them.

Social entrepreneurs, with their fitting into their socio-cultural impact, can catalyze systemic change or system transformation through innovation and implementation of new ideation that have an enormous potential to shift the current status quo. Social entrepreneurship combines a social value proposition, a wide-scale business system, and lasting functionality for change for the benefit of society (Osberg and Martin, 2007). Social entrepreneurship, as I have mentioned, is not only for non-governmental or non-profit work, but its acumen defines and highlights *an entrepreneurial work that prioritizes transformative social impact while pursuing financial sustainability*. While social enterprises can have non-profit or for-profit legal structures, they share common denominators that, in fact, as essential elements to be considered as a social enterprise: 1) a social impact mission: a clear goal or objective to improve lives and/or the environment; and 2) a business model: a strategy for how an enterprise will create or craft, deliver, empower, and capture value in a sustainable manner (Acumen Academy, 2021). Silent empowerment through the driving effect of social entrepreneurship, denotes praxeological philosophy, that humans engage in purposeful behavior, contrary to reflexive behavior or other unintentional undertakings. Silent empowerment reflected on Fig.3 leading to Fig. 4 and how it turned out, portrays praxeological behavior—one

cannot consume something that you do not believe or would not do it yourself if given the opportunity. The efforts of social entrepreneurship and silent empowerment are vital factors in shifting the social and cultural landscape into a more sustainable and beneficial development.

III. Social Entrepreneurship

Vignette Five

“Workplace Advocate”

5.1

“This does not stop here,” I say so to myself. “Can it be two or three things at once?” I ask so to myself, too. I have been offered various opportunities in the academe and I do not want to turn them down and lose them because I know that I can contribute something, and probably, it will be an additional platform for me, too, to share my experiences, excel in the field, and have the chance to influence people regarding social entrepreneurship and my advocacy.

I have paused my career in the academe to give way to my social enterprise and be a mother, but what if I can do all? I know I will never find out if I would not even try, but I also know that it would not be an easy feat not only for me but also for my enterprise and my child. Probably, what I also need is an institution that supports both of these takeaways, not that I have to give up one thing for another, but would it be possible, really, to have everything all at once and be provided support by an educational institution? If my work ethics serve me right, I know I can be disciplined enough especially with my time to do it all at once.

5.2

I came to work at the University since they are preparing for further expansion in the country. I believe that this is a good opportunity for me to hone my leadership skills more which may enable me to also further my entrepreneurial abilities.

My past experiences could help but it would not hurt to have new ones. Since I am advocating for the environment and education, these platforms – being employed – would be a great help not just to my talents but also financially.

I always think about how my master's degree would help me and proceed to my graduate studies then (and post-graduate), one huge determinant for me is to also work in an academic institution to use the knowledge and skill sets that I have built and learned throughout my years in graduate studies. I have been inspired to lead by our University Chancellor who is both teaching and leading administratively, the Vice Chancellor for Academic and Finance who is also doing both and even publishing substantial research that contributes to the body of knowledge. I think it is fitting to adopt such a mindset and discipline if I want to achieve something professionally and academically.

I feel welcomed in this University I have been recently hired in. I have introduced myself with all my experiences in both corporate and academic, as well as my entrepreneurial experiences entrepreneurially. I see that they are rather impressed, as perhaps I can be an addition to the roster of leaders who have a background in entrepreneurship that can contribute to the University's development towards becoming one of the most competitive universities not only in the country but also internationally.

5.3

I feel supported by the management and my colleagues. I have started telling stories about my enterprise and started introducing my products and what I do, on top of the things that were assigned to me at work to accomplish. I do feel, given the leadership position and leading a huge team across different campuses, I may be able to gain traction as an entrepreneur, social entrepreneur, at that, and contribute to the goal of the university to introduce sustainable ways and green efforts in the school and its stakeholders.

While time management could be a bit challenging because of the full-time work in the university and its demands, I am grateful for the opportunity to lead and inspire people.

Though there are some aspects I would definitely like to change or improve, learning here with this entrepreneurial mindset can serve as a huge potential.

I moved from one campus to another as I took on more challenging roles in the Admissions Office as the university is currently undergoing expansion. My skills expand, too, and all the more I gain attention not just because of where I am from, but of what I actually do outside of my work at the university. It is enticing to think that my tiny platform (as I can see it) can mean huge for others especially when I get to the part where I can share my stories. I went to Bacolod with my bosses for another expansion campus and I got to see a social enterprise based there that employs deaf workers to can crab meat for exportation. It was a purposeful experience that validates how a social enterprise can affect the community and its direct stakeholders, not just about offering products and/or services that can benefit the clientele but also provide livelihood opportunities to persons with disabilities, the marginalized, and the local rural communities that are in need and in search for dignified source of income. It was inspiring as a start-up business and a novice social entrepreneur to see that operations are possible and employing individuals who are also in need can serve upliftment not only of their economic status but also their purpose in life; that despite their disabilities, financial status, and educational attainment even, or lack thereof, they have meaning and the prowess of such is resulting to productivity and uplifted personal resolve.

5.4

As a social entrepreneur and a full-time employee in the academe, my schedule may be challenging to manage because of everything that must happen all at once, but I rather see it fitting because the challenges or the disadvantages outweigh the advantages that I experience being both. I gain more credibility and if I do, Happy Shift gains the same level of credibility, too. It takes a lot of discipline as an advocate, you have to lead by example, practice what you preach, and show consistency in everything you do—your resolve as a social entrepreneur also serves as your reflection as an employee in an educational setting. It was difficult for me to separate myself from both,

so I unified my discipline and incorporated one with another. In this case, I do not have to change hats; besides, I would rather be known as the employee who is also a social entrepreneur and vice versa, and milk on the credibility that was breadth into me when I accepted the full-time job in the academe. I would not want it any other way anyway. I want to aspire and inspire people in the university community, I am closer to my main target audience—the students. In this manner, I can see directly what was changing in the market and economic landscape that can therefore help me navigate through social entrepreneurship and share it with the community I tap into, who, wholeheartedly, make various products to ensure that they can earn in whatever manner, in however flexibility and versatility they can employ to ensure income. It was a lot of pressure for me, of course, but with the attention and the platform that I currently have, I see that not all people have the same, so I would rather be grateful than immense myself in tiresome ways, but all the more privilege to somehow hit two birds with one stone and communicate my advocacy with another hat on my head. Time and time again, I climb the academic ladder, from a mere Supervisor all the way to being an Assistant Director, and eventually a Director, the experience opened a lot more doors for me as I gained more consideration and have been exposed more to the academic organization as a whole given the position that was designated to me. The first thing that came to my mind when I was promoted to the director-level position was how this would also make a difference for Happy Shift given the power that constitutes my credibility as a university official, communicator, administrator, and advocate at the same time. Aside from the work assigned to me and my responsibilities, I was empowered as a leader to showcase my talents and skills; hence, given the opportunity to lead an office and use what I am good at for the benefit of the organization and elevate my skills. There are many more people I can tell my stories to and an added medium of being invited to various speaking engagements about my social enterprise and my experiences as a leader. Various organizations I meet or would like to meet me are for both my academic work and my social entrepreneurship experiences—all of those I am always willing to share and inspire people on no matter how small my voice sometimes is. I always keep in mind that what I do may not be as big as how the leading competitors in the industry do it, but instead

of being threatened by such reality, I convert it to something more productive—to get inspiration from what they do and be able to follow their footsteps in combination with my unique experiences, learnings, and knowledge.

I was so nervous to be in front of people but given the credibility I have gained and things I wanted to say, I take courage for everything I do. My advocacy speaks for whatever I do and realizing these handful of transitions in my professional life, I know that I can do both. Looking back from when I started in 2016, I am grateful that despite the challenges, I have come this far and still consistent with the journey although still being challenged from time to time, being a social entrepreneur, I have been shaped and have been profoundly influenced by my childhood and school experiences and thus have remarkably driven my decisions and actions. Many times, during my talks, I have been asked, “Why do you do the things you do?” The shortest answer I can manage to say is, “to create a difference,” but I also manage to reflect on that, aside from creating a difference, I am also driven to learn and to feel; and I have that desire to satisfy and be satisfied to do business, to create a livelihood for others, and to communicate my advocacy.

Immersion to Vignette Five

Being a social entrepreneur was and is not easy. Building a business from scratch is not a walk in the park given the other responsibilities that one may have, I, for one, am a mother, a student, and a full-time employee, too. I used to think that being an entrepreneur or a social entrepreneur may also shy me away from academic work or the hustle and bustle of being an ²¹employee in an educational institution; however, the full-time employment also made me a better person and more importantly, a better leader. In Fig. 5.1, I restarted my career in the academe after a two-year-long maternity leave at that time and started my social enterprise in 2016. Start-ups are incredibly hard, financially wise, and a full-time job to support

the business could be necessary and incessantly required. I had my doubts as a social entrepreneur if I would be able to survive being a 3-in-1 but immersing myself in the field of entrepreneurship and my social causes has contributed to my situation. I forego certain entitlement that has built into me that comes when starting a business—startups were not as glamorous as it may sound and being an owner and founder is not as sophisticated as it sounds. Being a social entrepreneur is about the social cause, the profitability, and the tenets of being a competitive entrepreneur. It was not much about the social status and the prestige—the accomplishment as a social entrepreneur and an SE is what matters.

In Fig. 5.2, my early days in the university as a full-time employee did a lot of adjustment for me as a person. I am an employee and thus, it concludes that I do not make all the calls and the decisions—there were still many layers above me that have the duties, responsibilities, and authority to conduct and create business decisions for the institution—far from what I usually do for my social enterprise, by which I, my own, is the sole decision-maker. It was a lonely and gruesome feat being an entrepreneur, a student, an employee, (and a mother), but I have learned a lot during my graduate studies—the hard work, the humility, and the purpose of why we do what we do. I take comfort in knowing that this hustle culture has given me some rewards—learning new things, skills, and balancing life, time management even, and making things work remotely well, especially during the onset of the pandemic. I take inspiration from UP Open University's Chancellor who does everything all at once with grace, honor, and excellence, and to whom I take affluence of being bestowed of an expertise related to social mobilization and advocacy. It was deemed possible for me, and it is feasible, though it was never without some pain here and there. In my early days in my new work, time was

always of the essence as I needed to be in one place and another quickly and efficiently. It honed my skills and re-created my social skills since I was exposed to people and school officials, and the bulk of my work was customer service. All of the hard work and application of what I have applied as a graduate student has helped me gain attention, not only as an entrepreneur but also as a leader. The university's top management's support to me as an employee, a talent, and a social entrepreneur, led me to various new experiences that made me a better leader. I was able to rank up, take a ²²leadership position, lead a team, and inspire people. While I believe that designation should not be a hindrance to a person to set culture, build goals, and inspire people, high ranks, especially when utilized rightfully, can inspire people, and gain recognition, and respect. A certain designation or position in the organization speaks or can equate to the credibility or being credible, with or without evidence of work most of the time. The designation of being a ²³Director helped me to become exposed to other aspects that made me witness that doing something for a social cause is evident and realistic—that despite the industry's challenges, it is still a viable business acumen. Such exposures have helped me see the initial eye view of the curriculum changes and the drive towards sustainability as more and more courses, companies, and organizations have started to adopt and incorporate SDGs in their business strategy and organizational missions. As evident in Fig. 5.3, I have been moved from one position to another and from one campus to another because of the discipline that I have secured through social entrepreneurial experiences primarily. All of such led me to promotions (Fig. 5.4),

“As a social entrepreneur and a full-time employee in the academe, the schedule may be challenging to manage

because of everything that must happen all at once, but I rather see it fitting because the challenges or the disadvantages outweigh the advantages that I experience being both. I gain more credibility and if I do, Happy Shift gains the same level of credibility, too.”

As I climbed the organizational ladder, my promotions also empowered me more as a leader and a social entrepreneur. The certain status has been helpful for me in gaining more traction in what I do. People, especially people in the organization and potential industry partners, have been interested in me more and I have been able to communicate my advocacy on a larger scale due to the growing medium that my professional career currently has. Jumping through the ranks, the elevation, while it may not have been a walk in the park because of the challenges, has also immensely helped to secure my place, not only in the university but also in the foreseeable future for my social enterprise to further evolve and serve. Not only has my platform expanded, but more substantially, I have gained more confidence, I have been empowered more, and I have become more courageous to get myself more out there, communicate my advocacy, and my social enterprise, showcasing my core to people without much of hesitation anymore.

Reflection on Vignette Five

Having a Leadership Role or a High Designation in an Organization gains traction but is not a requirement

Truth be told, the higher you go up the organization ladder, the higher responsibilities you also have and the higher the credibility that you encompass across the institution. Having a leadership role or a high designation in an

organization can indeed gain traction and birth several benefits like 1) increase influence as you can help and be a tool in shaping or re-shaping the direction of the organization and your decisions provide significant impact on its success; 2) enhanced visibility, as someone who has a leadership role in an organization whether a huge or a start-up business, leaders like me are often in the spotlight and serve as the face of the organization. While there are many advantages to it, someone who has a leadership role should also be cautious on both professional and personal actions; and 3) impact on organizational culture, leaders have the power to shape organizational culture and set forth pertinent values that employees or other team members can follow. A leader's influence is vital in any institution as they can make or break the work environment of their organization. In my experiences, my leadership roles inside and outside of *Happy Shift PH* breadths influence not only the people inside the organizations but also to clientele. Hence, one's advocacy speaks volumes. The portrayal and integration of advocacy to one's belief is a significant determinant of how an organization can be successful and how far the brand will go as the leader and the people in the enterprise or institution embody the heed to resolve and act on the social cause.

It was also interesting to understand that you do not have a leadership role to influence. While leadership roles are just one conduit for influencing other people in and out of the organization, they are by no means the only way to create an impact. In my experiences being a social entrepreneur who joined the academe thereafter, I was not given a high leadership role at first take despite my professional experiences, entrepreneurial background, and educational achievements, but I have portrayed leadership and influence towards my teammates and other vital posts in the academic organization that led me to better roles or higher positions.

Some ways that helped me exert influence without holding a huge leadership title are the ways I have been able to practice and exposed to as a social entrepreneur such as 1) **expertise and knowledge**, my experiences as an entrepreneur create a significant influence on my colleagues because I was comfortable and confident to make business decisions on a daily basis that is related to the office mandate that was assigned to me; 2) **effective communication**, as my substantive areas involve business and marketing communication, and being supplied and graduated graduate degree in development communication, these helped me a lot in understanding theories and application related to communication that played a useful role in being an effective communicator in the workplace. Such skills helped me inspire, persuade, and motivate people, especially my teammates or colleagues either in a group presentation or one-on-one conversations whether on a personal or professional basis; 3) **lead by example**, being professional at all times despite the hurdles have been useful. As a social entrepreneur, every day is adversity at best especially when working under pressure, instigating and communicating advocacy, acting on it, and of course working for profit to further sustain the business. The practice in handling the daily operations led me to be a positive thinker and demonstrate professionalism, dedication, and a strong work ethic, which I was able to apply as a typical employee or a team member; 4) **emotional intelligence**, one cannot be an effective leader without being emotionally intelligent. I always believe that all work and duties can be learned and can be trained, however, work ethic and discipline are something to be prioritized and be able to adapt if one is trainable and displays emotional intelligence. As a leader, it is essential to understand and empathize with other's emotions that can therefore build strong relationships with people and influence them through showcasing our

genuine care about their well-being; and 5) **advocacy**, taking a stand on something—a social cause or any important issues and advocating for change has helped me foster influence of public opinion and mobilize support from like-minded individuals in the organizations that have been silently empowering or empowered by social causes and willing to act on their beliefs and personal advocacy as well.

Based on these experiences, observations, and other's episodes as well, it was essential to recognize that influence is not solely dependent on having authority or a formal leadership title, but it often hinges on credibility, trust, and the ability to build relationships with people in the organization. Thus, people are further influenced by trust, respect, and common goals and values. While non-titled individuals in the organization can still foster influence and have the power to reshape a culture, leaders have pertinent roles to maintain as well. While there are many challenges and responsibilities a leader like me has, success in these roles requires a combination of experience, skills, and adaptability. Moreover, ethical leadership, commitment, and advocating for the organization's values, beliefs, and missions are crucial for long-term organizational success and creating positive traction in a leadership role. Looking back and taking into consideration my current role being a social entrepreneur and one of the leaders in the academic organization, I have grown my responsibility further so that it already matches the role and the professional maturity that I aspire to. Indeed, leaders and bosses create a significant impact on their teams. As I experienced, I am also responsible for the mood, motivation, creativity, and performance of my team. It is essential that leaders in the organization, no matter what industry, become emotionally intelligent to create employee retention, increase productivity, and interject employee happiness—these factors are the keys to gaining a competitive advantage in

whatever field you are in (Arruda, 2017). Furthermore, people around you are also a factor in gaining respect and trust that can lead to success. Thus, making the right decisions based on the needs of the organization and your stakeholders is significant in certain leadership roles. A non-threatening environment breeds more creativity and humbles a leader no matter what his/her designation is (Macris and Reiter, n.d.). In this light, while higher designation can gain traction, being a leader does not duly equate to having a bigger position in the organization. According to Robin Sharma (2010), one of the world's leading leadership experts and a best-selling author,

“Leadership is not about a title or a designation. It’s about impact, influence, and inspiration. Impact involves getting results, influence is about spreading the passion you have for your work, and you have to inspire team-mates and customers,”

As a social entrepreneur, I can duly resonate with this quote, and all the more with this leadership book as it applies to realistic experiences and expectations in operating a business, more so a social enterprise. While there are many advantages to having a higher designation or position in the workplace or the organization, there are also higher responsibilities that come with it. Thus, the positions we are given, or we are employed by, breed credibility—whether we have it or not. It is automatic that people will look up to us even without fully knowing us because of the titles we may have or come within the organization. While this may sound advantageous to business operations and external representations, leadership is not about the position or a title, but rather an action and an example (Sharma, 2019). In the recent generation, the face of leadership is fast changing, and it is not about dominance or authority anymore, but more about collaboration and teamwork. My experiences, starting from the bottom of the organization, led

me to a leadership position and values that are humbled, perseverant, and reliant. While titles surely empowered me because of the many benefits that came with them, they surely humbled me too because of the array of responsibilities that were bestowed upon me. Thus, moving forward, with all the exposures I get as a speaker both about my social enterprise and how I do as a social entrepreneur, leadership and communication skills are the ones I shared that are essential in making the business operations and getting adherence to the climate of the organization.

Sensemaking: Leadership and communication skills are hard soft skills to learn

***Meaning Gained from Vig. 5:** Leadership skills are crucial to the success of a business as it can make or break an organization. Titles are advantageous but not a requirement.*

Vignette Six

“Advocating and Educating Through Storytelling”

“Happy Shift PH is a passion project and social enterprise (eco-enterprise) to empower and support the local community in the many how-to’s of all-natural, sustainable, and green living.

Happy Shift went through different positive changes throughout its early years. Today, it is a retail online shop promoting and supporting all-natural items that are sustainable, cruelty-free, vegan-friendly, and affordable for everyone.

We, at Happy Shift, advocate for the environment and livelihood supporting the local market. Our online presence is a venue to learn more about the environment, its struggles, and viable solutions to preserve and uplift it.

As an eco-enterprise, we provide a ‘shift’ to the usually consumed products with the commitment to deliver unceasing contributions for the benefit of nature, our homeland, and our kababayan.

A portion of our sales is being donated to various local organizations and individuals to support people who are in need, our nature, and our local community livelihood.”

*When I was writing the **About Us** section of my social enterprise, I could not help but look back to how it started and how it is going and tell many many stories I came to this point. Like many other entrepreneurs, I was also unsure of my initial journey, but it takes passion and determination to go along and continue. Part of our sales is being donated to various organizations advocating for the environment and education. Through Happy Shift PH, I have supported planting trees in Sierra Madre, joining the World Literacy Foundation (WLF) to be one of the representatives from the Philippines to advocate for literacy and education worldwide focusing primarily on Philippine efforts. Though all might be silent, I gain existence through students and their student organizations. In fact, this exposure has helped me to know who my main target audience is—students and the youth (students up to young professionals).*

Our presence in social media cannot be compared to other competing brands but can be in comparison with other social enterprises. In fact, I draw inspiration from other social entrepreneurs and their businesses on how I want to be and how I would be able to support and continue my advocacy. While we are bordering on silence, it is in silence that I hear the call of my audience as to what they would want to see, what they are willing to support, and how they would want to support it. In the various stories I tell though not televised or aiming for clout, indeed, like-minds do think alike. For someone who is also an introvert, most of my clientele are also silence supporters but are considered to be the most consistent in terms of advocating for their beliefs and supporting movements aligned with their advocacy.

More and more students whom I talked to and told stories to in the past are also approaching me that they have applied the advocacy in their daily lives and as I can see, more and more educational institutions are also prioritizing sustainability, social entrepreneurship, and integrating SDGs

in business programs to ensure the continuance of advocacy towards economic and social development.

In the many talks I was invited to or paneled on, I have witnessed a changing landscape in terms of business programs. Leading by example is also one way to silent empowerment, I must say. The more students see how you do it and how you are managing despite setbacks and other challenges, the more they are influenced to follow and do the same. Just like how I was inspired by other social enterprises and NGOs, I do the same (lead by example) so the youth or those who are interested in doing business with a social cause can also be inspired to start and persevere while it is not an easy feat, it is a rewarding field to be in.

Immersion to Vignette Six

Students' Career Day and other student organizations' business days and thesis and capstone workshops and defenses have opened many doors for me in terms of getting business exposure and sharing my knowledge in terms of being a social entrepreneur and a development communicator. In the many reflections I have had since the inception of *Happy Shift PH*, I have immersed myself in the fact that silence can be empowering. I was inclined to follow how other brands do it and compete with them in terms of social media presence, brand marketing, and other affluent noise that can gain more sales and establish a stronger brand identity. I would want that, definitely. But knowing the right audience is first and foremost, and it did come to me in realization when I was already being sought to speak in front of the student body to talk more about the story of my enterprise. Such exposures have led me to provide options to students to figure out how they are best to proceed with the help of my shared knowledge and experiences and introduce them to the current situation of our environment, our education system, and how we can able to provide help to those who are in need. It is subtly selling the information and communicating to them the need for support and the need for change through social

causes. In social media, I introduce the made, benefits, and advocacy the enterprise supports; in my talks and guest speakership lectures, I tell stories that can resonate with students and the youth—stories of experiences I have encountered in the past—and leave questions for the audience to ponder on. Silence can be empowering as it helps people voice their opinions and hear their own voices, take ownership of their thoughts and future actions, and assess their ideas—such silence can help people constructively engage (Gendron, 2016). Advocating and educating could be in a form of storytelling that can help build credibility, trust, and loyalty with the audience. It helped me to showcase my personality, my values, and my current social impact. In the current millennial generation and Generation Z (Gen Z), ²⁴storytelling has helped my social enterprise appear and be more human, authentic, and relatable to the audience. Storytelling, in high regard, is an art and science of utilizing anecdotes, narratives, emotions, and metaphors, to convey a message, communicate, and create meaning. It is not just about telling facts and sharing vignettes, but also about creating a memorable and engaging experience for the audience (LinkedIn Advice, n.d.). Storytelling is not just about using words, but also about using action. In my case, leading by example, and enjoying some silence and active listening to give space to the audience to ponder. While it is easier to feed them on what I think is right to do or things I know how to do, making them realize and drawing inspiration from what I do, my ways and my told stories are considered the most rewarding for me. Leading by example is also not easy as communication and leadership skills, while considered soft skills, are hard skills to learn, but worthy of learning.

I am inspired by ²⁵various social enterprises that are already huge and influential in the country. And for me, they do lead by example as well. More than

business they propagate the social cause and advocacy they believe would be better for their audience. I, being one of those audiences, am also affected by such advancements and progression because not only do I learn more about the advocacy I support, but I can also situate and reflect on their developments, so I would be able to apply them to my own social enterprise and share to my audience. A leader's ability to influence group behavior through exemplary action has potential effects through leader organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). This said model suggests that OCB may be promoted directly or indirectly through enhancing people's belief that OCB is worthy (Yafee and Kark, 2011). In this light, social influence is said to be mobilized and be an aid to others to attain a collective goal (Chemers, 2001, p. 376). This chain of information sharing, educating, and persevering with the advocacy, are capacitating to me, albeit silently at times, but empowering all the same.

Reflection on Vignette Six

As a social entrepreneur and a communication scholar too, we tend to utilize analysis to persuade others, but there is substantial evidence indicating that people are more likely to be affected by stories. In this way, we are not only engaging with their minds but also in their imaginations, values, and emotions (Ho, n.d.). In social businesses like mine, there is a power of storytelling as it compels us to educate and advocate leading to inspiring action. Indeed, storytelling can also provide positive emotional connections with the audience and drive them to be part of the cause, because even if they do not experience the challenges of problems first-hand, they can resonate with the people through emotions. Matching these stories

with compelling actions and integrating them into values and development of character, honed my leadership skills and communication styles and helped me guide others through my behavior and actions instead of only with my words. Role modeling with storytelling or leading by personal example has been recognized in many leadership theories. In these experiences, I see that both the skills of telling stories and leading by example are crucial to connecting and influencing my audience. Storytelling in leadership and putting learnings from experiences into action craft a great story. It captures attention, delivers resolutions, leaves a lasting impression, and even builds tension that triggers action and participation from the clientele or the audience. It helped me lead authentically and it built my credibility to further be invited to several engagements and be recognized by institutions through my contribution to society and economic development though I may not be as big as others. While recognition can serve as fuel for me to continue what I do, feedback, sales, and support (sales) from my audience are the best motivators and drive to further innovate and continue what I have started. Hence, of the plans that I am compelled to do—doing a dissertation on advocacy communication of my social enterprise, making sure that it is readable to an array of audiences, and being able to convert this into a book, and/or present to international and local platforms to widen my voice, communicate the cause, influence others, and strengthen my social enterprise and the brand. Being consulted and being invited to different business programs and student activities have made my storytelling better and my leadership skills validated. They are an affirmation that I am doing something valuable, influential, and significant. My inspiration and wisdom gained from different organizations I was affiliated with and employed by have been beneficial in making me the social entrepreneur I am today. Through words and actions, this

aligned with the AC theory that communication extends far beyond mere words, but also in action; and is always communicative, thus, all, in consideration as to whether there is verbal or nonverbal, even to the most subtle and unconscious degrees.

Sensemaking: Storytelling is a driver of positive change.

Meaning Gained from Vig. 6: *In the realm of social entrepreneurship, storytelling wields power that serves as a vehicle for advocacy, education, and the inspiration of action. Stories create positive emotional connections with the audience and compel them to join and support the cause. Even those who have not experienced the social challenges firsthand can resonate with the emotional depths of this advocacy communication and its narratives.*

Vignette Seven

“My Vision of A Social Enterprise: Happy Shift”

In this class, I gained an in-depth understanding of social entrepreneurship and I have learned how it was aligned with what I was doing since 2016. Before I ventured to [putting] up a business and actually having a cause, I was an active volunteer in various movements for the environment. Subsequently graduating with a business degree, I initially thought of putting my own business apart from my endeavor in the academic field.

Somehow, it already dawned on me to craft something for a larger cause – a cause bigger than myself, the recognition, and my desired [for] profit. Being an advocate for the environment, I was exposed to different challenges that our country and our nature, for that matter, face.

Being a tiny fish in the sea of entrepreneurship, I braved the field to create even a slight difference. Which, looking back, I know I am not there yet; however, I am glad that I have already started and have quite spread the word on how we could be able to help with our own little effort.

Background: The Happy 'Shift'

In 2016, I was a struggling young professional spending nearly a decade in both the [academic] and corporate fields. It was also the time that I have celebrated a year in graduate school. I was juggling studies with all these jobs feeling that there was still a void to fill.

I have started crafting my vision of a business - not labeling yet if it will be a commercialized one or a social enterprise. Back then, I just thought that I needed to be able to do something—mostly for myself. But doing it only for myself was not fulfilling. It will not fill the void. More so, it will only make it worse.

When I was starting to tap various manufacturers and suppliers for a business focus and offering still unknown then, I recognized marginalized workers who give businesses affordable products that are being sold way too expensive in the market. These workers get an estimate of 0.03 percent of the total retail prices and sometimes even lower, almost for free.

I could not help but empathize and I felt that 'need' to do something. That was the exact time I knew that I needed to get going. Happy Shift PH was born.

Rationale

***Happy Shift** is a passion project to empower and support the local community in the many how-to's of all-natural, sustainable, and green living.*

Happy Shift went through different positive changes throughout its early years. Today, it is a retail online shop promoting and supporting all-natural items that are sustainable, cruelty-free, vegan-friendly, and affordable for everyone.

We, at Happy Shift, advocate for the environment and livelihood supporting the local market. Our online presence is a venue to learn more about the environment, its struggles, and viable solutions to preserve it and uplift it.

We provide a 'shift' to usually consumed products with the commitment to delivering an unceasing contribution to the benefit of our environment and our homeland.

Product Offerings and Benefits

Happy Shift offers a range of products from makeup, bath, face items, and products for home & and living, and [continuously expands] to novelty and other artisan collections. All are made from all-natural and sustainable materials.

These products benefit stakeholders—mainly local manufacturers (marginalized workers), local businesses (for other supply needs), and consumers. Happy Shift assures that all products are safe to use and made affordable for consumption.

Happy Shift products, while do not have approved therapeutic claims, are mostly derived from real and natural ingredients. We refuse to put chemicals on our products so as to not cause harm to consumers.

In the long run, we aim to be a one-stop shop for the daily needs of the Filipino people. We are for everyone. Currently, our markets are mainly from the masses and middle-income earners. We aim to turn every customer to be an advocate for the environment [and education] and help with our mission and vision to help the local community and provide all-natural and sustainable products for the nation.

Our Value Proposition

We aim to maintain financial sustainability in the long run, but we believe that putting a huge margin will not help one of our main stakeholders, our consumers. We, therefore, adjusted how to manage our finances and how we spend; thus, not making our customers suffer by purchasing costly products. We want to venture that supporting our local products is better and more affordable. After all, we are making the products in the Philippines for the Filipinos.

While we, after all, are an enterprise, we do not want to be known to be high-priced. We offer premium products at the most [affordable prices] possible. We want to have a share in the social market.

We aim for social change. We want the market to help the environment and gain traction and effort through word-of-mouth in terms of [marketing and] promotions.

- *Submitted as an essay entry to the Certificate in Social Entrepreneurship (2019) under UP Open University Massive Open Distance eLearning (MODeL) with Course Coordinators Dr. Melinda dP. Bandalaria, Dr. Primo Garcia, and Mr. Larry N. Cruz*

Immersion to Vignette Seven

Stepping into the narrative of Vig. 7, I have embarked on what I call a ²⁶transformative journey, seamlessly blending my passion and mission for environmental and educational advocacy and profound business endeavors. I was a budding entrepreneur who began exploring social entrepreneurship, though the term was still not vivid as I would not want to self-proclaim, and gradually realized the alignment between my academic pursuits and my evolving mission and passion into one. In the world of business, I was driven by the desire to create something greater than myself, greater than my personal gain. While I am ²⁷for-profit, I am for my advocacy, too.

I was a tiny fish in the sea of many experts—entrepreneurs and social entrepreneurs at that and I dared to make a difference, albeit small and gradual. Looking back on such experiences, I acknowledged that I was on the road to making an impact, even if it was just modest in the beginning. As I delve into what I have accomplished during that time, I know that I can do more and that I can do so much better. It was filling in the void I had in me, but it was more than that as I went on because the inception of a business idea, initially and primarily for personal gain and fulfillment, hinted at the restlessness within me.

My turning point came when I interacted with different marginalized groups and workers and learned their stories. It sparked unfairness and that empathy I felt gave birth to the idea of my new social enterprise, Happy Shift PH. This business

venture is aimed at empowering and supporting local communities and promoting all-natural, sustainable, and affordable products.

Happy Shift PH has developed over the years, transitioning into an online retail platform offering and championing products that are not only eco-friendly, all-natural, and cruelty-free, but also locally made and locally sourced in the Philippines. My brand's advocacy for both the environment and education crafts support for local livelihoods as its core, and an online presence that serves as an educational platform for understanding environmental issues and solutions, establishing a connection to the community, and educating the public on what we can do to help the social cause. Instead of seeking large profit margins, too, my main focus was making all-natural and sustainable products accessible to the masses, encouraging advocacy for the environment and education.

My value proposition for *Happy Shift PH* centers on promoting social change as I aspire to have a market share, especially in the social market field (e.g., NGOs, social enterprises, and nonprofits). I duly aim to inspire consumers to support the cause and share their experiences with others, in any way possible and they are able to, fostering word-of-mouth as a primary movement to promote (storytelling) and of course advocating by changing their way of thinking, of living, and behavior towards a sustainable future.

Reflection on Vignette Seven

Proving Principles of Effective Advocacy Communication

Reflecting on Fig. 7, I saw the compelling testament to the transformative abilities of advocacy communication as it seamlessly constructs the threads of environmental and educational passions and entrepreneurship. This reflection to Fig. 7 explores how I resonate with advocacy communication principles, focusing on the importance of empathy, alignment, and of course, social change.

Passion and Purpose

My social entrepreneurship journey underscores the significance and magnitude of alignment between personal passion and a higher objective or purpose. In advocacy communication, advocates often succeed when their passions and personal values are on par or in harmony with their chosen social causes. In this light, my deep-rooted passion for environmental and educational advocacy became my motivation to create and pursue my social enterprise. According to Maibach, Roser-Renouf, and Leiserowitz (2010), individuals who align their personal values with their advocacy efforts are more likely to persist and achieve their goals and/or objectives.

Human Connection and Empathy

My exposure to marginalized workers has opened my eyes to the current situation and that also drove me to take *Happy Shift PH* as one of my valuable pursuits. Empathy also aligns with advocacy. In fact, advocacy communication often hinges on the ability of an individual to connect with the emotions and

experiences of others. Empathy serves as a powerful tool in driving support and action, as it crafts a genuine connection between advocates and their audience (Cohen, 2009). My found and experienced empathy for the marginalized served as the key to the advocacy.

Authenticity

Advocacy communication requires authenticity. It plays a significant factor in advocacy efforts, as it builds credibility and trust that also play crucial aspects in mobilizing and advocating (Cone, Feldman, and DaSilva, 2003) for *Happy Shift PH's* social cause. Such authenticity for the brand, its products, and its marketing, are able to resonate with the audience or consumers who are also seeking genuine, ethical, and authentic brands or products. Honesty can go a long way as I always believe it is, not all might like certain authenticity, but honesty knows no rehearsal, so it is easier to manage and act upon.

Social Change Through Communication

When I think of my proposition and where it centers, it cores on social change. Thus, emphasizing the role and use of communication in driving advocacy. In fact, as a social enterprise, I rely more on communication to inspire the market to join the cause and advocate for the same movement, leading through example, so others can also. Reflecting on this, these efforts align with the diffusion of innovation and the power of interpersonal communication in influencing behavior. My approach leverages the principles of advocacy communication—recognizing that individuals are more likely to adopt new behaviors (e.g., lifestyle changes,

supporting a cause, etc.) when influenced by their peers and trusted sources (Rogers, 2003).

My social entrepreneurial efforts core on advocacy communication—it highlights the significance of aligning personal passion with greater purpose, empathizing and connecting with others and their experiences, and driving social change through authentic and persuasive communication (whether verbal or non-verbal).

Sensemaking: Synchronizing personal passion with a loftier purpose.

Meaning gained in Fig.7: Advocacy communication has a transformative power that illuminates the significance of aligning personal passion with greater purpose, demonstrating empathy, driving social change through communication, and upholding authenticity in the enterprise's advocacy efforts.

Vignette Eight

“The Social Enterprise”

During the onset of the pandemic in 2020, we were just happy to have survived the year and we have become hopeful of how 2021 will be. Indeed, there was hope for us, and we think that this year has been better compared to the last.

Personally, we also lost loved ones this year due to the pandemic. It was also a hard time for us to continue because of the on-and-off pandemic and how we would be able to leverage the market. We did great and we wish to do more, of course. This year has also been kind to us as we have introduced new products under our brand and we [are grateful] you guys are still there supporting us.

We have been lucky to have been invited to several webinars and virtual conferences. We have introduced and talked about ourselves [and what we do] to students in Indonesia, shared our best practices with students of De La Salle University - Manila Young Entrepreneurs' Society, presented our learning to students of CFA, and shared some of our insights as a social enterprise and made acquaintances too with the students of La Consolacion College - Caloocan.

We want to thank all of you for your usual support of all-natural, sustainable, locally made, and locally sourced products. We want to show our deepest gratitude to all of you who believed in us and supported our causes so we may be able to support other causes as well.

This 2022, we will double. This year, we will persevere more to bring these products near you and definitely, we will expand our product offerings to tend [to] your needs. Thank you for joining us in our advocacy, this year po ulit! Marami pong salamat at mabuhay po kayong lahat.

—

Happy Shift PH, since it [was] just only an idea and not an enterprise yet per se, has been committed to the betterment of the community, understanding a need, and addressing those needs by providing sustainable solutions.

We get a lot of questions as far as our community-based brand is concerned like: why do we not appeal to those who are on the poverty line? Our answer is simple: we want to appeal to those who have the ability to help and are willing to understand what those on the poverty line are going through because being with them, we see material stuff does not appeal to them [as] they always fight to live another day [and survive the day]. But those who can understand shall understand and we hope that we can hold our hands together to reach a common goal: to extend comfort, change a system, and develop the community through education and love for the environment.

All of these might sound impossible. We know that we have a lot of problems we cannot solve in our lifetime, we are just glad to have started. And through inspiring others, may we continue the work, may we not stop, so little by little we can attain what was meant from the very start.

We are one with the World Literacy Foundation in taking part in a global initiative to eradicate illiteracy and functional

illiteracy through the platforms that we currently have. We believe that literacy can also help people to understand how much our nature is suffering and through it, we may all exert an effort to take care of it; at the same time—learn to educate ourselves about the truth and nothing less.

Moving forward, as we always commit to advocating for the betterment of the environment and education through literacy, our platform will not only be for retail but for also championing ideas that aim to educate, engage, and encourage people to support projects with greater causes for the benefit of nature and the masses.

With every order we sell, five percent (5%) of [the] total [order] amount is being donated to education, environment, and community causes we support. Some of such causes are uploaded on our website and social media pages for transparency. As we improve our products and services, we aim to be more transparent about what we do. We aim for more partners and an initiative to support through and through.

Thank you to all of you who have been with us since the beginning. We promise to offer more locally and sustainably made items for you and continue with this advocacy.

—

Hello, everyone!

I am happy to be with you all again this year as we celebrate our 7th year as an enterprise! It was not an easy ride especially when the pandemic hit, but like all of you (from whom I take inspiration []), this business continued to strive and ensure to offer (and eliminate, if I may say) products that be of helpful to your daily lives, to [your] sustainable living, at that!

This new year, Happy Shift PH will venture into making our deliveries [eco-friendlier]. We have always struggled with logistics in the past because it is always a trial and error and most of the things, we cannot control; however, we see that we can do something about delighting you in every purchase made.

Originally, we really do not buy some of our logistics packaging like bubble wrap, boxes, plastics, for example. We were just re-using those materials from our own deliveries as we do not want them going to waste; so, we see the point of

re-using them and at least [avoiding] litters piling up. This year, we opt not to use those anymore and we encourage our suppliers to do the same or manage our own pick-up [as an alternative].

This 2023, we want to be more presentable [for you], our dear clients, without causing much harm to our environment and contributing non-biodegradable waste to our landfills. We are fully embracing a better way to transmit to you your parcels safely and of quality.

*From bubble wrap, we replaced it with **honeycomb paper wrapping papers**. To better secure your packages, we now opted for **corrugated boxes** where we also put product information and thank you cards (also an addition this year!) to guide you with your purchase, your sales invoice (SI) as your right to have a receipt on your every purchase to ensure that your transactions with us are legitimate, and with them is our love and gratitude for your support with this endeavor.*

We are grateful for your support, and we are happy that you are [with us] in this advocacy together!

—

We are grateful for all the e-mails and social media messages we receive from advocates, clients, and most especially, students, sharing with us their research and other content made for/about Happy Shift PH.

We are honored to be part of your study and ultimately humbled that you chose us, our brand, as one of the subjects of your great pursuits.

Thank you very much.

We are overjoyed and grateful for the love and care you show our brand. We are honored to be part of any of your studies and humbled that you chose us as one of the subjects [of] your great pursuits.

Almost every day for the last two weeks, we have constantly received e-mail and social media messages about marketing research, content, and articles about Happy Shift PH made by researchers, students, and advocates highlighting how much they love our products and opportunities we can explore based on the feedback of the clientele.

With this, we are indeed thankful.

*We cannot begin the excitement, really, of venturing onto something **NEW!** In the coming -few months, you may witness our gradual transition, especially in our branding and offerings.*

As we prepare for our 8th year this 2024, we are delighted but all the more challenged to bring our clientele and growing audience what they need, want, and desire, aligned with our advocacy of supporting and offering [locally made] and locally sourced products.

We are ecstatic to deliver more products your way, albeit different from what we used to, but we are going bolder, better, and stronger as a social enterprise and an advocating brand towards our cause of promoting our local goods.

We will go big in this transition as we are stepping outside of our comfort zone, but one thing is for sure: Happy Shift will still remain Happy Shift, more colorful than ever.

Immersion to Vignette Eight

In my Vig. 8, I embraced resilience and adaptability, especially during the tumultuous years of the pandemic. In 2020, when we faced unprecedented challenges, I was only aiming to survive and luckily, 2021 felt a little more hopeful and better. *Happy Shift PH* did not close down, and it remains operational. Personal losses cast a shadow despite the glimmers of hope and optimism. The health crisis had taken over loved ones, clients also were thrifed to make ends meet, and they too lost their loved, ones, and survival was one, if not their only priority during that time. Through also the unwavering support of my clientele, *Happy Shift PH* managed to stay alive and even introduced new product offerings.

Amidst all the adversities and challenges in the last three years, I was surprised to see many invitations to different webinars and virtual conferences to explain the social enterprise and share my stories as a social entrepreneur. I have

even extended my social business's reach in Indonesia and huge universities like De La Salle University, La Consolacion College - Caloocan, and the Catholic Filipino Academy (CFA). The support from my growing audience was indeed a testament to the value of my social mission.

Through the years, what I can do is express my heartfelt gratitude for the unwavering support of the community. In this light, I have recognized that my mission was not just about selling products but also about inspiring positive change in others. I am all the more committed to community betterment, identifying the needs of my audience, and providing sustainable solutions as my evident approach since day one. While many may have doubts or questions, I see that I stick to the goals of extending comfort, effecting systemic change, and developing communities through education and environmental stewardship. I, personally, recognize the enormity of the world's problems, and as a social entrepreneur, I remain undaunted. I recognized that the journey had already begun, and my role was to inspire others to continue the work. I believe in the power of literacy to craft understanding and promote environmental conservation and sustainability.

In this ever-evolving journey of social entrepreneurship, I have pledged to allocate five percent of every total amount in order to support education, environmental causes, and community initiatives I feel strongly about. I aimed for transparency in my operations and one of my goals is to seek more partners and initiatives to champion. The path that I am taking in fully embracing my social entrepreneurial mindset and title drew inspiration from the supportive community. During 2023, I tend to commit more—this is making sure that all deliveries are eco-friendly. I transitioned from non-biodegradable packaging to eco-friendly alternatives, including corrugated boxes and honeycomb paper wrapping. This said

transformation aimed to elevate the customer experience while minimizing the environmental footprint we consume.

Reflection on Vignette Eight

The Power of Advocacy Communication

My experiences as a social entrepreneur also personally serve as an inspiring example of adaptability, resilience, and an evident power of advocacy communication. This reflection not only demonstrates *Happy Shift PH's* journey but also provides valuable insights into the field of advocacy communication that cores on the profound impact of storytelling and community engagement. The challenges in the pandemic had a remarkable impact on resiliency in the face of adversity and the power of hope and positivity breadths evidence in advocacy communication, where inspiring stories or narratives and actions can motivate, inspire, and mobilize individuals (Frandsen and Johansen, 2017). Empathy and shared experiences play a great role in advocacy communication, too. Empathy, as a communication tool, builds an authentic connection between advocates (social entrepreneurs like me as well) and the audience (Cohen, 2009).

Webinars conferences speakerships and lectureships like I have experienced also underscore the importance of community engagement which is also pertinent in advocacy communication. Such engagement with a community strengthened the impact of my advocacy efforts and inspired others to advocate for these social causes and join the initiatives (Andreason, 2006). My gratitude towards my social enterprise's supporters is overwhelming; thus, reflecting on this, aligns with the core principles of advocacy communication, where its goal is often to

inspire positive change (social change, for one). According to Peattie and Peattie (2003), advocates who focus on more than just their services and product offerings are more likely to succeed in inspiring action. This is also due to the shared and resonating commitment to community betterment and the focus on the right target audience in terms of emphasizing the importance of aligning advocacy with shared values and a common understanding with the community itself. The power of storytelling is ever-present in my advocacy communication strategies through the years of social entrepreneurship. Indeed, stories can be imperative tools for inspiring change by connecting with individuals' emotions and values.

Sensemaking: The transformative potential of advocacy communication underlines the profound impact of storytelling and community engagement.

Meaning gained in Fig. 8: Social entrepreneurship with an inspiring journey of adaptability, resilience, and community engagement through effective advocacy communication strategies can ignite positive change.

My Contribution to Social Entrepreneurship

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

In the context of social entrepreneurship and my exposure and experiences in the field as a social entrepreneur and in the academic field, both fields have immersed me in the understanding that leaders play a vital role in promoting Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), a concept defined by Dennis Organ in 1988, among their subordinates or team members. OCB refers to the efforts of employees to act and to behave as good citizens within their organizations, though not formally rewarded in a formal manner, results in effectiveness when collaboratively performed or practiced by a group (Organ, 1998). The good act of behavior may be discretionary and voluntary that often exceeds the person's formal job description or responsibilities; thus, can contribute to the success and well-being of the organization. While such behaviors are not expressed fully rewarded or recognized, these are significant and essential for fostering an optimistic and productive work culture, which is also important in the social enterprise sector, or in the academe, at that. Practicing and committing to OCB, without duly known to me initially, is my one good contribution to the realm of social entrepreneurship. As a social entrepreneur with advocacy at heart and advocacy communication strategies in mind, the social causes I have studied, exposed to, and participated in, alter my behavior and impact all facets of my life—both personally and professionally, to become a contributing member to social change. Through such experiences that I have shared via vignettes, OCB gave me depth to have the following keys and factors to be a more effective advocate and social entrepreneur that aspiring social entrepreneurs themselves can also practice:

Lead by Example: Leadership is an essential part of the social entrepreneurship communication process. As a leader, I have to demonstrate ideal behaviors that I also want to see my team members perform. Through consistently engaging in various acts of leadership and citizenship, I was able to set standards for others to get inspired about and eventually, follow.

Craft a Culture of Purpose: As a social entrepreneur, my work centers on having a higher purpose—addressing social causes such as environmental issues, illiteracy, and many others. It is important to me that my organization and the people around me or I choose to be surrounded by share the same values and mission. While others I have to work with may have a different perspective and preferences, cultivating a culture of purpose and advocating for a social cause can do no harm. When people or team members in the organization believe trust in the mission and the purpose of the said cause, they are more likely to engage and adapt in OCB to express their support.

Create Opportunities for Involvement: As a social entrepreneur who is also an introvert, being involved also has some challenges. Many introverts may also relate that getting involved sometimes drains their social battery. However, with the right platform compelling storytelling, and other advocacy communication strategies, there are many ways to connect with the community. Some may be comfortable just leaving comments on social media or sending direct messages to express their thoughts. The most effective way to involve the community of the audience is to have social

initiatives that they can resonate with through platforms that they are most comfortable utilizing (e.g., social media, e-mail, snail mail, etc.).

Be an Effective Communicator: In order to promote OCB in the field of entrepreneurship, leaders or social entrepreneurs must know how to maintain open communication channels to ensure community engagement can continue and inform the audience about the organization's current social advocacy, impact, goals, and progress.

Practice Resilience, Flexibility, and Adaptability: The last three years have been very crucial in both the business side and social cause of every social enterprise and other businesses for that matter. The field of social entrepreneurship, while breadth a lot of potential and success stories, carries various challenges, as well. It is a dynamic environment that demands adaptability, resiliency, and flexibility, as there are moments of experiments, uncertainties, and learnings, may it be through words and experiences, or mere observations in this emergent field.

With all these personal accounts and exposures in and out of the field of social entrepreneurship, OCB can be considered a driving force in achieving the social enterprise's missions and creating a positive impact. Advocates and social entrepreneurs who understand the value of OCB and actively participate in its promotion can have long-term success in terms of addressing social causes and gaining profit effectively and manageably.

Silent Empowerment: The Transformative Power of Storytelling through Action in Advocacy Communication

In my studies and scholarship in communication and as a social entrepreneur, first and foremost, silent empowerment has dawned on me during years of exposure to doing business with social objectives. The firsthand experience of seeing how my audience perceives *Happy Shift PH* products gave me something to explore and ponder in terms of my advocacy and communication strategies. The concept of silent empowerment, while eliminating the usual form of clout in the reception of the current generation, also focuses on the idea that storytelling, as a form and a tool of advocacy communication, transcends traditional verbal, written, and digital communication. Silent empowerment is a dynamic approach in which people or organizations ascend and scale their actions to influence and inspire others. Storytelling through actions and leading by example becomes a forcible tool for driving social change, emphasizing and focusing that it is not solely dependent on words, but rather, on the profound and astute impact of real-life advocacy efforts.

Silent empowerment supports the 'actions' of any word said. This idea of storytelling, a form of advocacy communication, showcases how fundamental it is to communication. Stories, often and ideally conveyed with emotions, experiences, values, behavior, and connections, have been traditionally linked with narratives shared and opened through words and written materials. Silent empowerment, in this context, explores and conveys powerful communication messages not just through the traditional form of words and written content, but primarily through actions (e.g., support, research, social media reactions and sharing, mobilization, active listening, OCB, life alterations, character development, etc.). In this sense, it

embodies that “*actions speak louder than words,*” and those who perform silent empowerment as a way of supporting advocacy or establishing a movement focus on creating a tangible impact in society, in the community, or even only in their circle of influence, believing that such participation may draw change.

There are many advantages and powers of silent empowerment that could be rewarding to social enterprises and their entrepreneurs. As I often observed and remarkably affects my entrepreneurial mindset, silent empowerment builds and carries credibility and authenticity as if it surpasses traditional communication methods. Advocates engaging in silent empowerment embody credibility as they are grounded in real-life deeds that make them authentic. Authenticity is significant in any social cause as it prompts trust from the community or the target audience. Empathy, on the other hand, is an essential piece in effective communication. It is also an organic product of silent empowerment. This trait demonstrates genuine commitment to understanding the audience and therefore executing actions that essentially answer to their needs. This advocacy communication method has therefore made *Happy Shift PH* the social enterprise it is today. Different and not directly competing with other players in the same field, silent empowerment, when performed by the audience through influences and a domino effect, can signify social change. As a social entrepreneur, I exemplify values to the best of my ability, to inspire others to follow suit. Storytelling through action gives full potential and motivation to the community to advocate for the same social cause and draw optimistic transformations in an individual and society. While silent empowerment is promising and does not need much clout to be sustainable, there are some ethical implications that advocates must consider. In my experience, there are also some misconceptions, communication barriers, and the need for consistent and

persistent efforts. In the realm of social entrepreneurial challenges, it was tempting to do what everyone else was doing, to follow what everyone else was seeing, and to practice what everyone else was expecting. But, as I have tried and followed such delegations and societal norms, I have come to witness that its impact does not drive towards a sustainable landscape nor affect the foreseeable future. Silent empowerment might be tedious and low on impact but persistently doing it can be tenable for the years to come. While it was tempting to trend and join the clout, the true value of the social enterprise lies in its tenacity, its mission and vision, and its sustainability for the years to come. All actions lead to long-term efforts for social change and uplifting the quality of life in all forms; thus, communicating such advocacy requires transformative sustainable actions.

The Definition and Value of Social Entrepreneurship

As a social entrepreneur, I also struggled not knowing the real meaning of social entrepreneurship, hence, I initially did not label myself as one during *Happy Shift PH*'s initial years of conception. In my research, while social entrepreneurship is an emerging and promising field, its exact meaning may vary. This research, through my experiences as a social entrepreneur, and with the help of valid narratives recorded, I, therefore, recognized the actuality of this field and its pursuits.

Social entrepreneurship refers to pursuing purposeful and socially driven business processes with equal prioritization to its profitability. It surpasses traditional corporate social responsibility approaches, as it is not

merely an auxiliary business afterthought but centers its conception and existence on its social causes.

In this contribution, I have found meaning in social entrepreneurial pursuits. Through moments of doubt, I have gained better clarity with the help of experiences, reflections on my work, and lessons learned in and out of the corners of my social enterprise. In recent years, I have not seen my business processes as socially inclined as I have always known that social entrepreneurship does not adhere much to profitability which is also my priority as a business entity. However, as much as social businesses prioritize their social advocacy and mission, they also have an equal foothold with prioritizing revenue or financial gains. Financial viability is pertinent in a social enterprise to ensure continuity of social efforts and advocacy and ensure business sustainability to ensure dependable and longitudinal undertaking to achieve and maintain the advocacy. Truly, the aim of social enterprise is to create innovative and sustainable business solutions to societal issues and challenges and safeguard its unceasing potential to further social good.

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

As a social entrepreneur, there was an intensifying reasoning for going into this field of social entrepreneurship and advocating for social causes. Questions as to why chose to go into this field also exist. Questions of why how, and what is next are often heard. I also often wondered. There were many doubts as to how I, as a communication scholar, could venture into the emerging field of social business. How being a communication scholar can be a viable tool to amplify business endeavors and was it better to focus on the business landscape rather than deepening the understanding of how such advocacy is being communicated, or all of these are just plain marketing, given my exposure in marketing as I majored on this field during my years in college. Such doubts cast upon me also provided points of clarification and later became my clarity through the help of experiences, social exposures, volunteerism, and mentors in both fields of communication and entrepreneurship. I have come to answer my *why*, and with all honesty, at first, it was just to get out of the corporate system and the usual expectations set by my current environment but later on transformed into a whole bigger purpose that holds greater meaning.

In this chapter, I wrap up by offering a recap of the results of this autoethnographic study aimed to answer as communication research. The methodology and writing of this research were guided by philosophical assumptions of *ontology* or 'what we know' and *epistemology* or 'how we know it'. The results of beliefs and experiences acquired through our lifelong involvements and learning and written here as vignettes, privileged the perspective of "I" in this research. Through these assumptions, *teleologically*, the acquired in-depth understanding of

personal narratives and the assumption of their reason and ends navigate the purpose they serve rather than the cause by which they rose; and that *praxeologically*, as a social entrepreneur, this autoethnographic study provided me the liberty to free once were muted perspectives in this field.

In fact, going through different facets of business, communication, and other related passions could be confusing for some as I hold many different hats. I am quick to revert that when I was asked what I do, I am a social entrepreneur and a communication scholar first and all else second. However, furthering knowledge in these fields is ever-challenging, as well. The more you know, the more you know nothing; and like what Doc Sandy mentioned during one his lectures, “*the higher you go up the academic ladder, the more uncertain you become of your truths,*” and to me, those uncertainties are humbling and meaningful as it creates bounds of growth and further learning to do. In fact, when I first presented this dissertation proposal leaning towards social entrepreneurship, I had a doubt that perhaps this study would be much more aligned in business than in communication, but just how clever Dr. Flor always is, he motivated me that “*business process is a communication process,*” and with much encouragement by Doc Mel, whom many classes in graduate school I always looked forward to, autoethnography in my experience as a social entrepreneur would be suitable in furthering my interest to accomplish this study.

The research questions I aimed to answer in this research on advocacy communication, privileging my voice as both the researcher and social entrepreneur are:

1- As a social entrepreneur, how do I accomplish my advocacy?

2 - *Why is silent empowerment a key social and cultural factor in my advocacy and social entrepreneurial activities?*

3 - *How can I contribute to the field of social entrepreneurship?*

Through autoethnography, I have adopted and applied techniques of recollection of social entrepreneurial experiences and exposures leading to social entrepreneurship ventures through vignettes which guided the textual (Taylor and Van Every, 2011) *immersion* to the details of anecdotes and experiences, *reflections*, and *modeling* or connecting realizations to make senses of the experiences and answer related questions about advocacy communication in social entrepreneurship.

The vignettes or anecdotes, just like how Rosete (2019) presented them and derived from Deetz (1982), have resulted in knowledge creation that enables the forming of information and contribution to the body of knowledge and the field of social entrepreneurship. Knowledge Creation through the perspective of Deetz is:

“a method that makes it possible for interpretive research to produce valid knowledge: one that does not follow a prescribed format or the existing standards of the research community but develops from traditional canons for text analysis that are firmly, empirically, and philosophically grounded.”

To delve into the nuances of the journey and exploration of personal perspectives in this research, these guiding theories and principles summarize and articulate the motivations and philosophical assumptions contributing to more insightful reflections on the significance and role of advocacy communication in the field of social entrepreneurship:

Table 1. Summary of Guiding Theories and Inputs

Guiding Theories	Inputs
Ontology	<p>The ontological position I have presented in this research revolved around my journey as a social entrepreneur and communication scholar, highlighting the importance of my personal experiences in understanding social entrepreneurship and advocacy communication.</p> <p>Wearing different hats helped me emphasize the evolving nature of my identity, roles, and existing challenges in navigating these roles.</p> <p>My initial motivations and doubts, as well as transformative shifts in purpose and advocacy, emphasized my ontological exploration of the reasons behind my choices and actions.</p>
Epistemology	<p>The epistemological position I have presented in this research leans on interpretivism and constructivism as I engaged in reflection and self-analysis—the employment of vignettes that explored my personal narratives.</p> <p>My personal experiences, reflections, and even doubts suggested a focus on subjective understanding—my reflexivity as an autoethnographer. This aligns with interpretivism, which highlights the significance of the interpretation of experiences and their meanings, and constructivism as knowledge is actively constructed by me based on my experiences.</p> <p>The use of anecdotes and vignettes (e.g., social exposures, the role of mentors, volunteerism, school experiences, environment, etc.) to construct knowledge signifies the essentialism of personal narratives as the core source of information.</p>
Teleology	<p>The teleological position I have presented in this research aligned with my purpose-driven approach emphasizing the end goals or outcomes and the greater meaning recognized from my journey (e.g., my initial desire to escape the corporate field to a transformation into a more profound purpose of</p>

	<p>being an entrepreneur—focusing on the end goal that holds greater meaning).</p> <p>There were also clarifications through experiences, volunteerism, mentorship, and social exposure and interactions, that teleologically, emphasized how and why these experiences provided me with ultimate purpose and clarity in the realm of social entrepreneurship through advocacy communication.</p>
Praxeology	<p>The praxeological position I have presented in this research emphasized my practical considerations, real-world experiences, and the full application of my understanding that stemmed from my immersion and engagements in the fields of social entrepreneurship.</p> <p>My decisions and reflections were rooted in my journey since childhood, as a scholar, and as a professional that contributed to my overall understanding of advocacy communication in an applied and tangible context (e.g., my practical considerations towards social entrepreneurship were rooted in my background being a communication scholar. My exposure and social interactions signify learning and understanding through real-world experience and practical engagements).</p>

In conclusion, my journey as a social entrepreneur, albeit an introverted one, has given me treasured insights and awareness into the ability of silent empowerment, specifically in the digital landscape. The transformative ability and character of storytelling as a tool through various digital mediums led to contributions and actions from my known audience—primarily college students and young professionals. These efforts have led conversion of regular online visitors and customers to advocates, which is what *Happy Shift PH* has been inspired to do and one of the cores of its very existence. I accomplish my advocacy communication through the use of digital platforms that enable my business

operations and cascade the advocacy and/or social mission of my social enterprise. These mediums have empowered me to reach a broader set of audience to truly identify who my market really is and further the communication of my social enterprise's values and advocacy more effectively and conveniently. Indeed, the significance of using technology such as online platforms and other digital social tools for propagating advocacy cannot be discarded, especially in this digital age where online presence, engagement, and reach are paramount.

The concept of silent empowerment in both digital and traditional landscapes in this context as how advocacy communication is also being accomplished emphasizes de-clouting and the importance of realistic engagements and actions by both the social enterprise and the audience. In this sense, I conclude that *actions speak louder than words*, and more so the number of likes, engagement, and noise on social media or other digital mediums do not guarantee conversion to advocates that can further support the social enterprise's social cause. Silent empowerment leans more towards the embodiment of the advocacy from one customer to another that influences lifestyle change and character development, as how I as a social entrepreneur strived to also *lead by example* and personify my advocacy into real-life actions and way of life. This approach, as explored through vignettes, proved that behavior and changes to it for the betterment have been demonstrated to be more sustainable, meaningful, and valuable; thus, creating an enduring impact. As part of the analysis through autoethnography, I also discovered the role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (Organ, 1998) and its significance in a social enterprise's advocacy communication. OCB plays a vital role in creating and influencing a positive and productive work environment in organizations and is pivotal for employees or other internal stakeholders to exceed expectations and

surpass their usual job responsibilities to further contribute towards the success of an organization.

Silent empowerment proves that it is a fundamental factor in advocacy communication as it introduces and strengthens a social brand's credibility and authenticity—both are essential determinants of establishing and maintaining trust and encouraging engagement from the target audience. This approach especially resonates with the generation that values credibility and authenticity as primary considerations of commitment and support. Silent empowerment is imperative in the social and cultural context in terms of social entrepreneurship as it allows better favorable and sustainable development. Silent empowerment, in conclusion, is a compelling social and cultural factor in the advocacy communication of a social enterprise, as it comes to trust, authenticity, and lasting impact. It promotes and upholds a sense of empathy and shared purpose while allowing individuals the opportunity to engage with social causes in their unique ways. In social entrepreneurship and as a social entrepreneur, banking on silent empowerment has been helpful in building impactful and productive connections that drive meaningful efforts, and social changes, and convert the audience to aspirants, advocates, social entrepreneurs, and development professionals.

In retrospect, advocacy communication is commensurate to the overall pursuit of social entrepreneurship. Through the value of OCB as part of the result of silent empowerment, focusing on advocacy communication can further influence and strengthen a social enterprise's social missions, mobilization, and audience engagement. Through such discoveries, my experiences and exposures humbled me and encouraged me to further my social enterprise's purpose. By providing a definition and meaning of social entrepreneurship, sharing narratives of

experiences through vignettes to resonate with the audience, and ensuring continuous efforts to champion the impact of *Happy Shift PH* as a social enterprise, advocacy communication has been a relatable and encouraging concept in communication to adopt, primarily because of the following reasons:

- **Driving positive change:** advocacy communication can encourage individuals to know more about the advocacy they are inclined with and craft their own efforts towards answering and providing solutions to social causes.
- **Building and strengthening awareness of social causes**
- **Triggering participation and civic engagement:** advocacy communication is more than just communicating through promotions and advertising; it is a form of storytelling that also aims to touch the hearts and minds of the audience to influence them to participate in social movements or support an enterprise that advocates for social solutions.
- **Empowering audiences and communities:** advocacy communication can empower both audiences and communities as it serves as a tool to influence change in both local and global aspects.
- **Promoting social responsibility:** through a creative approach like advocacy communication, a social enterprise can easily hasten the

impact of social responsibility and how it is significant to be part of both the audience and other relevant stakeholders.

- **Influencing public policy:** advocacy communication can breathe into initiatives that can influence public policy at both local and national levels. Efforts and changes in behavior like OCB and silent empowerment alongside their influences can heed the call to introduce policies that can strengthen, protect, and scale up advocacy communication initiatives and its core advocacy. MSMEs do face a double burden of adopting the usual taxation scheme of a regular business while building its social cause which can also mean sharing their profit with their initiative (Ito and Shanaz, 2019)--this study and its advantageous results of the impact, may this breadth public policy that can help my fellow social entrepreneurs in terms of technical business stances to ensure our social businesses' sustainability.
- **Aspiring individuals and institutions to pursue and participate in social entrepreneurship.** In ensuring the potential that public policy for social enterprises can be in place, I hope, and I definitely work on discussing participation in pursuing social entrepreneurship, especially for the students. Creating public policy and pursuing research like this, may light the way for the national agencies for education to integrate social entrepreneurship into the students' curriculum and inspire educational institutions to introduce and prioritize social entrepreneurship and its related fields.

- **Global Impact:** advocacy communication processes and their effect in terms of behavioral change, customs, and systemic change can deliver impact to a global capacity.
- **Opening research opportunities:** the same with my experiences in social entrepreneurship, knowing it, and even not knowing it initially, advocacy communication is more than just a communication process, as it opens many research opportunities through curiosity, philosophical assumptions, current know-how, and current real-life and social situations. Advocacy communication, teleologically, captivates, emotions and furthers knowledge in certain social agendas just like social entrepreneurship or social business as a field.

The exploration of advocacy communication in an SE and its existence thereby brings out the fundamental answers to why I do what I do and why aspirants should also participate in it and pursue this same field. Some are able to resonate, that at first, it was just to get out of the corporate system and maneuver a career onto something else—something more enjoyable and valuable perhaps, but later on transformed into something bigger that holds greater meaning. The ‘why/whys’ has gotten deeper through the years. This study answers and fills in the gaps in terms of social entrepreneurship, its impact and advocacy communication, and how it operates from the perspective of the social entrepreneur itself.

Recommendation

This research makes use of reflective writing, a way of processing the practice-based experience to produce learnings that integrate theory and practice interpret reflections and identify the learning outcomes of such experiences (University of Reading, n.d.). Reflective writing examines *personal experiences, events, ideas, and information* with a personal writing style that looks for meaning and analyzes personal responses to experiences, events, thoughts, and feelings, and their significance; in addition, it does not limit an individual to academic evidence (University of Hull, n.d.). This study supports the following recommendations:

To social entrepreneurs (especially introverted ones), this study investigates the specific techniques and processes that introverted social entrepreneurs can use to leverage digital channels. Identifying the best practices and further analyzing the role of digital mediums in fostering a sense of community in this niche could be facilitated, as well as the impact of early childhood experiences and school exposure on the development of the social entrepreneurship interest of an individual.

To social entrepreneurship aspirants, this study explores the motivation and life experiences of a social entrepreneur and how they lead to impactful pursuit to the field as a form of mission and career. It appeals to a more exploration of other in-depth accounts of social entrepreneurs to know their other motivations to pursue and/or even challenge the said field.

To the communication practitioners and scholars, the long-term effects and implications of advocacy communication specific to silent empowerment can be

explored especially its cultural and societal influence that can contribute to social change. The concept of OCB could be ideally investigated to know how an organization can effectively promote this concept and deepen the understanding of its potential to drive positive societal and cultural changes.

To the research community, cross-disciplinary research could be a valuable addition to the body of knowledge as it can bring favorable insights from different fields of business, psychology, communication, and sociology that provide a more holistic approach and understanding of advocacy communication as a sub-field, the context of social entrepreneurship, and their integration to one another.

To advocates and the general society, this study fosters some understanding of the influences and drivers of advocacy, its communication, and creating a platform that can be beneficial for them and for their causes. Exploring this research and crafting related studies in terms of advocacy communication as a sub-field of communication, social causes, and their implications, and the impact of social entrepreneurship in culture and society can provide valuable insights into these contexts and can forward us to a more functional economic and social terrain.

This dissertation went through a lot of reminiscing and reflection of all the past hard work, drivers, drama, and pain of research and filling in the gaps of what has to be constituted into writing. In this manner, I was able to gain confidence in my experiences and let go of the 'impostor syndrome' that I was not good enough and that my work was not as valuable as others'. I wish to share that despite all the challenges I have faced through the research undertaking and all the self-doubts I have learned to get peace with, I now can say that I am undoubtedly a solid and full-blooded social entrepreneur and an advocate who spearheads advocacy communication in a manner I am most invested in and know-how; and that, it does

not stop there, but going forward and within to find light and clarity that I can offer, not only to my organization but also to the people around me. Through silent empowerment, I was able to validate that clout is not everything nor it is the only way to be successful in this field, but indeed, *actions speak louder than words do*, and that silence could be an admirable avenue to reflect and gather like-minded people and people who have doubts too for them to see that resplendent fields of communication and how it can be a valuable tool in the field of social entrepreneurship.

CHAPTER VI

IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This autoethnography study of analyzing advocacy communication in my social enterprise unmuted my voice brought the understanding of silent empowerment and even discovered the role of storytelling and OCB as crucial elements in my pursuits. Recognizing silent empowerment is crucial in terms of advocacy communication strategies in my social enterprise as it focuses on genuine action that has long-term implications on how I can engage my audiences, get their support in my advocacy, and convert them to be advocates of the same cause/s I support.

This autoethnography research has been a personal pursuit as much as it is an academic/scholarly one because it ignites my confidence to share my experiences given my introvertedness and some impostor syndrome here and there. While I have achieved quite a few already in the field of business and communication, as well as the academe, I remain steadfast in humility that somehow borders on self-doubts if I am gratified to share ideas with others. Thus, this study has validated me and my work in more ways than one, which I want to further on and share with students, scholars, and the rest of the general public to be their resource material or even some ordinary reading that perhaps they could resonate with or learn a thing or two. I have validated through this autoethnography research journey that social entrepreneurship is a transformative force that equally encompasses both doing social good and prioritizing business profitability.

This autoethnography study and as an autoethnographer in this research journey imply that personal experiences have a place in scholarly research. Citing

the claim of Ellis, Adams, and Bochner (2011), “autoethnographer not only tries to make personal experience meaningful and cultural experience engaging but also, by producing accessible texts, she or he may be able to reach wider and more diverse mass audiences that traditional research usually disregards, a move that can make personal and social change possible for more people” (p. 277). This research has opened me up to the world and more importantly in the field of communication and social entrepreneurship, as “researchers do not exist in isolation,” (p. 281).

Finally, this study can leverage the power of storytelling and OCB as factors in the success of advocacy communication of a social enterprise. Students, aspirants, and the general public can benefit from this study to understand a part of communication that deals with advocacy and campaigning for a social cause.

Future Directions

This research aims to fill the gap in advocacy communication in social entrepreneurship. This serves as a support to the study of Cornejo, Kam, Arch, and Nylund-Gibson (2022), which tests advocacy communication theory or ACT as multidimensional – *minoritized people can engage in communicative strategies at the interpersonal, mediated, community, organizational, and policy levels to challenge oppression*, in this study’s case, to find analyze how advocacy communication is being accomplished and received by the audience of a social enterprise. Albeit there are a lot of studies I can still think of after accomplishing this, I wish to pursue storytelling of experiences to further engage with the audience—and this is a starting point and finish the book that I am currently working

on regarding Sustainable Leadership and all other unmute voices in the field of social entrepreneurship in the perspective of a communication scholar. There were many books written about entrepreneurship by business leaders and advancing theories by entrepreneurs themselves; while they are all valuable and attested to the understanding of a business concept and procedure, communication scholars play a crucial role in communicating such processes in a way that is more interesting, especially to those who do not have a mere idea about social entrepreneurship and advocacy. Being a communication scholar is an advantaged role that encompasses both the science and art of business and communication, as again, I repeat, from the words of the wise Dr. Alexander G. Flor, “business process is a communication process.”

This is the most modest attempt I can come up with to shed light on social entrepreneurship and my experiences as a social entrepreneur—whether I knew it then or not—but at least I know now. Moving forward, I wish to do more synthesis about advocacy communication and further apply its theoretical perspectives in customer behavior and other communicative research. In the future, I aim to know more stories and I wish that this study can unmute as many voices as possible, and I wish to live long and prosper to listen and see it.

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APPENDICES

Superscript No.	Evidence/Declarations
1	 <small>DEAN OF THE INSTITUTE</small> </p>
2	</p> <p style="text-align: center;">“A Study on Effects of Consuming Plastic and Styrofoam Materials Used in Selected Fast-food Chains in the University Belt”</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Submitted By:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">██████████</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> Leader: Hostalero, Shainne L. Asst. Leader: Picache, Siden Marie C. Members: Azuela, Robert Michael V. Gregonio, Camille S. Limbo, Merzela A. Matibag, Aphoglean D. Pena, Michelle D. Salibio, Mary Jane B. Solitario, Rachelle Ann N. </p> <p style="text-align: center;">Submitted to:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Dr. Joselito P. Jera</p>

3

Conclusions

- Styrofoam materials affect the health of the consumers by infection by its chemical toxicity which would cause cancer and other sickness.
- Toxic chemicals leach out of these products into the food that they contain which these chemicals threaten human health and reproductive systems.
- The usage of plastics and Styrofoam eating utensils affects the environment through the improper disposing of these utensils.
- Fast-food chains really benefit with plastic and Styrofoam materials through convenience, affordability, accessibility and time saving.

Recommendations

- Paper, wooden or bamboo materials, corn plastics, and silverware (reusables) are some of the alternatives that the fast-food chains could use.
- The government can convert these plastics and Styrofoam materials through energy so that we can make use of the disposed materials and less pollution for the environment.
- The possible actions to be done as students, suggestion boxes would be of great help, creating advocacies, communication to DENR, creating blogs through social network sites, and by institutionalizing these policies.
- Possible actions to be done to effectively implement solid waste management in the fast-food chain industry are by following the protocol of the company regarding waste management.

4

5

RSVP: Invitation to Greenpeace Volunteers' Orientation ✕ 📧 📧

 Oscar Gador <oscar.gador@greenpeace.org>
to Francisco, David, bcc: me

Mon, Feb 9, 2015, 1:09 PM ☆ 🌐 🔄 ⋮

Dear Volunteer,

First of all, thank you for showing interest in defending this fragile planet and believing in the campaigning work of Greenpeace.

You are cordially invited to attend the Volunteers Orientation of Greenpeace Southeast Asia (GPSEA) - Philippines.

When: February 21 (Saturday) TIME: 1:00 PM - 5:00 PM

Where: Greenpeace Office, 2nd Floor JGS Building, 30 Sct Tuason corner Sct Lazzano, Diliman, Quezon City

Check this link for map location:

<http://maps.google.com/maps/ms?msid=216039296097428228180.0004899b3c96e8c2416048msa=0&l=14.631081,121.032311&spn=0.00571,0.009645>

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REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
CITY GOVERNMENT OF MANILA
OFFICE OF THE MAYOR
BUREAU OF PERMITS

ELECTRONIC BUSINESS PERMIT - RENEWAL

Owner's Name: ALESSA SHAINNE LIM HOSTALERO	BIN: 117-00-2020-0200414
Business Name: HS ORGANIC PRODUCTS	Permit No.: 2024-00000075
Address: JUAN LUNA ST GAGALANGIN 2720-A, BARANGAY 185, TONDO 17 II, NCR, CITY OF MANILA, FIRST DISTRICT, 1013	eOR No.: OR-2024-0000083-B
Telephone No.: 2518967	Date: 01/02/2024
Email Address: Happyshiftph@gmail.com	Time: 08:21:51 PM
No. of Emp.: 2	Amount Paid: 14,012.00
Area: 4.00	Barangay No.: 185
Nationality:	

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11

Unibersidad ng Pilipinas
Mabuhay!

Hinuonod sa batas ng Republika ng Pilipinas at batay sa rekomendasyon ng Kolehiyo at pagpapatibay ng Konseho ng Unibersidad, ipinaghaloob ng Lupon ng mga Rebolente kay

Alessa Shaimme L. Hostalero

na nakatupad sa mga itinakdang pangangailangan ng Kurso, ang titulong

Master sa Komunikasyong Pangkaunlaran

kasama ang lahat ng mga harapan, karangalan at pribilehiyo, gayundin ang mga obligasyon at pananagutan kaadibat nito. Ipinaghaloob sa Los Baños, Laguna, Pilipinas, ngayong ika-26 ng Setyembre ng taong dalawang libo i labing-siyam.

DANILO L. CONCEPCION
Pangulo ng Unibersidad

MELINDA G.P. BANDALARIA
Parasela ng UP Open University

ROBERTO M.J. LARA
Katimn ng Unibersidad

ALEXANDER G. FLOR
Dekano ng Kolehiyo ng Araling Pang-impormasyon at Komunikasyon

12

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

CERTIFICATE OF ACCOMPLISHMENT

is awarded to

Alessa Shainne Hostalero

for having completed the Massive Open Distance eLearning Course
on **Social Entrepreneurship**
(16 Hours of Training)

Issued on 19 December 2019.

Dr. Melinda Bandalaria
Course Coordinator
Dr. Primo Garcia
Course Coordinator

Mr. Larry Cruz
Course Coordinator

13

VERIFIED

CERTIFICATE of ACHIEVEMENT

This is to certify that

Alessa Shainne Lim Hostalero

successfully completed and received a passing grade in

ASD001: Age of Sustainable Development

a course of study offered by SDGAcademyX, an online learning initiative of SDG Academy.

Jeffrey Sachs
Professor
Columbia University

 VERIFIED CERTIFICATE
Issued August 16, 2020

VALID CERTIFICATE ID
3b6d4d063ff475ea12c30fa94d473e2

14

Ratings & Reviews of Happy Shift Reusable Cotton Rounds Set

4.9/5

40 Ratings

★★★★★	38
★★★★☆	1
★★★☆☆	0
★★☆☆☆	1
★☆☆☆☆	0

Product Reviews Sort: Relevance Filter: All star

20 Feb 2021

★★★★★
Aileen J. Verified Purchase

Thanks happy shift tuwang tuwa ako dahil may freebie and wala talaga akong nakitang plastic sa loob ng packaging thanks talaga always na ako bibili sa inyo. Thanks din lazada mabait si kuya na nag deliver and saktong lang sukli ko 😊😊😊

Color Family Combination

15

16

Opening Remarks:

*Ms. Heidee T. Esteban, BSTM IV
Head-Secretariat, Events Class Committee*

Keynote Address:

“RECONNECTING: Business and Service Now and Beyond”

*Hon. Bernadette Romulo-Puyat
Secretary, Department of Tourism*

Awarding of Certificate of Appreciation to the Keynote Speaker

“Turning into a New Leaf: An Eco-friendly ways and Sustainable Living/Green Practices in the Service and Business Industries”

*Ms. Shainne Hostalero
Owner/CEO
HS Organic Product (Happy Shift Ph)*

Awarding of Certificate of Appreciation to the Resource Speaker

“The Super C’s of Customer Service that Create Loyal Customers”

*Mr. Eugene Yap
President, Hotel and Restaurant
Association of the Philippines (HRAP)*

Awarding of Certificate of Appreciation to the Resource Speaker

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23

Shainne Hostalero, MDC · You
Social Entrepreneur | Communication Scholar |
Academician
8m · 🌐

I'm happy to share that I'm starting a new position as
Director of Business Development and Linkages
Office at National University - Philippines!

Starting a New Position

24

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27

Dear Alessa Shainne Hostalero,

Welcome to the **LESA 2023 (LEADERSHIP FOR ENTERPRISE SUSTAINABILITY ASIA)**, proudly hosted by the Asia School of Business.

Searches from the web/internet

“quotes from Mother Teresa”. Accessed at

<https://www.goodgoodgood.co/articles/quotes-about-making-a-difference>